

Reduced Entries Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 12

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

Magic and PanMagic: <http://bit.ly/4lGECNN>

Semi-magic: <http://bit.ly/4f1GChn>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **magic**, **panmagic** and **semi-magic** squares of order 12 for the **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries** we understand that instead of considering 144 entries in a sequential way, we are using **non-sequential** entries in less numbers. These **non-sequential** entries may be **positive** and/or **negative numbers**. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values. It depends on the type of magic square. Initially, the work is written in terms of letters instead of numbers and then are followed by examples. These kind of magic squares sometimes we call as **algebraic** magic squares. The complete work is composed of 57 different types of magic squares of order 12. Out of them 28 are **magic**, 4 are **panmagic** or **pandiagonal** and 25 are **semi-magic** squares. In this work we bring total 32 different ways of writing **magic** and **panmagic** squares of order 12. By **panmagic** we understand that the magic squares are **pandiagonal**. We have divided this work in two parts. This part is composed of **magic** and **panmagic** squares. The second part is with **semi-magic** squares of order 12. In case of **semi-magic** squares some conditions are also explained to change them in magic squares. These are based on four types of magic squares, i.e., **pandiagonal**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares. This work also include the idea of **magic rectangles**. In each magic square, the **magic rectangles** of same order are equal in width and length. For similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 10 refer Taneja [37, 38]. Previously, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36] also brought similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of magic squares. The work is extension and enlarged version of author's previous works. This is the second part only on **semi-magic** squares. The first part is of this work [39] on **magic** and **panmagic** squares.*

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1 Introduction

We have divided this work in two parts. This part is composed of **magic** and **panmagic** squares. The second part is with **semi-magic** squares of order 12. In case of **semi-magic** squares some conditions are also explained to change them in magic squares. These are based on four types of magic squares, i.e., **pandiagonal**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares. This work also include the idea of **magic rectangles**. In each magic square, the **magic rectangles** of same order are equal in width and length. Below are two table giving the details of algebraic magic squares of orders 3 to 12:

Orders	Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Total
3	1	0	1	2
5	1	1	1	3
7	4	1	3	8
9	10	1	9	20
11	12	–	–	12

Orders	Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Total
4	1	1	0	2
6	2	2	1	5
8	5	1	3	9
10	9	1	10	20
12	28	4	25	57

The table give above brings the revised version of author’s previous work [37, 38] for orders 3 to 12 except order 11. The revised version of onder 11 shall be given in another work. The author’s previous works [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36] based on similar ideas for the orders 3 to 12 brings the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of magic squares. These previous works brings less number of reduced entries algebraic magic squares. The web-site by F. Gaspalou [3] brings initial work on magic squares of orders 3, 4 and 5.

This is the second of the reduced entries algebraic **semi-magic** squares of order 12. It brings 25 different kind of **semi-magic** squares. The conditions to bring them as magic squares are also explained. For the first part on different type of reduced entries algebraic **magic** and

panmagic squares refer the author’s work [39]. All these 57 algebraic **magic**, **panmagic** and **semi-magic** squares are with two numerical examples. In case of **magic** and **panmagic** squares, the examples are for **even** and **odd** number magic sums. In some examples, the decimal entries are also considered. In case of **semi-magic** squares the numerical examples are for **semi-magic** and **magic** squares.

2 Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are six different examples of magic squares of order 12. These are based on sequential numbers from 1 to 144. These can be seen in previous works [24, 25, 26, 27, 28] of the author.

Example 2.1. *Let’s consider a magic square of order 12*

1	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

*It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12, where the blocks of order 3 equal **semi-magic** sums **semi-magic** squares.*

Example 2.2. *Let’s consider a magic square of order 12*

2	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12, where the blocks of order 4 equal magic sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4.

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										870	
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a magic square of order 12, where the four blocks of order 6 are magic squares of equal magic sums.

Example 2.4. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
	134	143	3	141	5	1	22	124	20	126	18	133	870
	16	113	108	38	106	40	36	26	120	24	114	129	870
	15	35	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	110	130	870
	131	111	45	86	84	57	90	58	60	100	34	14	870
	132	33	46	56	71	76	65	78	89	99	112	13	870
	139	118	51	62	66	77	72	75	83	94	27	6	870
	128	23	101	64	80	67	74	69	81	44	122	17	870
	10	115	96	82	73	70	79	68	63	49	30	135	870
	9	29	95	85	61	88	55	87	59	50	116	136	870
	137	117	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	28	8	870
	7	31	37	107	39	105	109	119	25	121	32	138	870
	12	2	142	4	140	144	123	21	125	19	127	11	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a well-known **single-digit bordered** magic square. The inner blocks are magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10.

Example 2.5. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

5	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
	66	67	77	80	86	59	54	91	23	122	134	11	870
	79	76	70	65	64	81	41	104	118	27	18	127	870
	74	69	75	72	58	87	97	48	106	39	9	136	870
	71	78	68	73	83	62	44	101	28	117	141	4	870
	55	82	61	60	88	89	98	47	121	24	126	19	870
	90	63	84	85	56	57	100	45	31	114	140	5	870
	103	92	99	43	49	93	51	50	38	107	123	22	870
	42	53	46	102	96	52	95	94	120	25	135	10	870
	26	40	30	36	112	34	110	116	108	113	21	124	870
	119	105	115	109	33	111	35	29	32	37	14	131	870
	1	143	128	137	133	16	130	7	20	13	3	139	870
	144	2	17	8	12	129	15	138	125	132	6	142	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a **cornered** magic squares, where in each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal sums in each case. It contains magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 in the upper left corner.

Example 2.6. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										870
4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135	870
141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10	870
37	108	43	41	103	101	100	98	48	46	13	132	870
107	38	102	104	42	44	45	47	97	99	131	14	870
106	39	57	88	71	76	65	78	61	84	130	15	870
40	105	60	85	66	77	72	75	64	81	16	129	870
33	112	87	58	80	67	74	69	83	62	17	128	870
111	34	86	59	73	70	79	68	82	63	127	18	870
110	35	93	95	49	51	56	54	90	92	126	19	870
36	109	52	50	96	94	89	91	55	53	20	125	870
115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24	870
30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic squares where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal sums in each case. It contains magic squares of orders 4 and 8.

Based on these six examples we shall give below 32 different types of **algebraic** magic and **panmagic** squares of order 12 for the reduced entries. By **panmagic** we understand as **pandiagonal** magic square.

3 Reduced Entries Semi-Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are 25 examples of **reduced entries semi-magic** squares based on Examples 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6. These can be written as **magic sums** provided some conditions are satisfied. These conditions are given by

$$L = \frac{5}{6} \times R \tag{1}$$

$$T = \frac{4}{5} \times L \tag{2}$$

$$S = \frac{3}{5} \times T \tag{3}$$

and

$$M = \frac{2}{3} \times S \tag{4}$$

These conditions shall be applied jointly or separately these conditions depending on the type of magic squares. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the **magic** or **semi-magic sums** of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

3.1 Single-Condition Magic Squares

Below are results with examples of **semi-magic** squares resulting in magic squares just with one condition given in (1)

Result 3.1. *Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+A_{34}+A_{35}+A_{36}+A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{39}+A_{40}-2*A_{29}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{31}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{32}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{33}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{34}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{35}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{36}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{37}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{38}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{39}$	$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{40}$	$11*2*A_{29}-9*A_{50}-A_{30}$
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{41}$	$A_7-A_{23}+A_{15}$	A1	$A_{29}-A_7+A_{23}-A_{15}-A_1-A_2-A_3$	A2	A3	A7	A8	$A_{29}-A_7-A_8-A_9-A_{10}$	A9	A10	A41
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{42}$	$A_{21}-A_{28}+A_{13}-A_1+A_6$	A4	$A_{23}+A_{15}+A_1+A_2+A_3-A_4-A_5-A_{21}+A_{28}-A_{13}$	A5	$A_{29}-A_7+A_{23}-A_{15}-A_2-A_3-A_6$	$A_{14}-A_8+A_{13}$	A11	$A_7+A_8+A_9+A_{10}-A_{11}-A_{12}-A_{13}$	A12	$A_{29}-A_7-A_9-A_{10}-A_{14}$	A42
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{43}$	$A_1+A_2+A_3-A_4-A_{21}+A_{28}-A_{13}$	$A_{29}-A_7+A_{23}-A_{15}-A_1-A_2-A_3+A_5-A_6$	$A_{21}-A_{28}+A_{13}$	$A_{21}-A_{28}+A_{13}-A_1-A_2+A_4+A_6$	$A_{23}+A_{15}+A_1+A_2-A_5-A_{21}+A_{28}-A_{13}$	$A_8+A_9+A_{10}-A_{11}-A_{13}$	$A_{29}-A_7-A_8-A_9-A_{10}+A_{12}-A_{14}$	A13	$A_{13}-A_8-A_9+A_{11}+A_{14}$	$A_7+A_8+A_9-A_{12}-A_{13}$	A43
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{44}$	$A_{21}-A_{28}+A_{13}-A_2+A_4$	$A_7-A_{23}+A_{15}-A_5+A_6$	$A_1+A_2-A_{21}+A_{28}-A_{13}$	$A_{29}-A_7+A_{23}-A_{15}-A_4-A_6-A_{21}+A_{28}-A_{13}$	$A_{21}-A_{28}+A_{13}-A_1+A_5$	$A_{13}-A_9+A_{11}$	$A_7-A_{12}+A_{14}$	$A_8+A_9-A_{13}$	$A_{29}-A_7-A_{11}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$A_{13}-A_8+A_{12}$	A44
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{45}$	$A_{29}-A_7+A_{23}-A_{15}-A_3-A_6-A_{21}+A_{28}-A_{13}$	$A_2+A_3-A_4$	$A_{21}-A_{28}+A_{13}-A_1-A_2+A_4+A_5$	$A_7-A_{23}+A_{15}+A_1-A_5$	A6	$A_{29}-A_7-A_{10}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$A_9+A_{10}-A_{11}$	$A_{13}-A_8-A_9+A_{11}+A_{12}$	$A_7+A_8-A_{12}$	A14	A45
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{46}$	A15	A16	$A_{29}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	A17	A18	A23	A24	$A_{29}-A_{23}-A_{24}-A_{25}+A_3-A_{18}-A_{10}$	A25	$A_{18}+A_{10}-A_3$	A46
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{47}$	$A_{22}-A_{16}+A_{21}$	A19	$A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}+A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}$	A20	$A_{29}-A_{15}-A_{17}-A_{18}-A_{22}$	$A_{22}+A_{14}-A_6-A_{24}+A_{28}$	A26	$A_{23}+A_{24}+A_{25}-A_3+A_{18}+A_{10}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}$	A27	$A_{29}-A_{23}-A_{25}+A_3-A_{18}-A_{10}-A_{22}-A_{14}+A_6$	A47
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{48}$	$A_{16}+A_{17}+A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{21}$	$A_{29}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}+A_{20}-A_{22}$	A21	$A_{21}-A_{16}-A_{17}+A_{19}+A_{22}$	$A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{20}-A_{21}$	$A_{24}+A_{25}-A_3+A_{18}+A_{10}-A_{26}-A_{28}$	$A_{29}-A_{23}-A_{24}-A_{25}+A_3-A_{18}-A_{10}+A_{27}-A_{22}-A_{14}+A_6$	A28	$A_{28}-A_{24}-A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{22}+A_{14}-A_6$	$A_{23}+A_{24}+A_{25}-A_{27}-A_{28}$	A48
$10*2*A_{29}-8*A_{50}-A_{31}+A_{49}+A_{48}+A_{46}+A_{47}+A_{45}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{42}+A_{41}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}-A_{34}-A_{35}-A_{36}-2*A_{30}-A_{32}-A_{33}$	$A_{21}-A_{17}+A_{19}$	$A_{15}-A_{20}+A_{22}$	$A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{21}$	$A_{29}-A_{15}-A_{19}-A_{21}-A_{22}$	$A_{21}-A_{16}+A_{20}$	$A_{28}-A_{25}+A_{26}$	$A_{23}-A_{27}+A_{22}+A_{14}-A_6$	$A_{24}+A_{25}-A_{28}$	$A_{29}-A_{23}-A_{26}-A_{28}-A_{22}-A_{14}+A_6$	$A_{28}-A_{24}+A_{27}$	$9*A_{50}-11*2*A_{29}+A_{31}-A_{49}-A_{48}-A_{46}-A_{47}-A_{45}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{42}-A_{41}+A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{39}+A_{40}+A_{34}+A_{35}+A_3+6+2*A_{30}+A_{32}+A_{33}$
$A_{50}-2*A_{29}-A_{49}$	$A_{29}-A_{15}-A_{18}-A_{21}-A_{22}$	$A_{17}+A_{18}-A_{19}$	$A_{21}-A_{16}-A_{17}+A_{19}+A_{20}$	$A_{15}+A_{16}-A_{20}$	A22	$A_{29}-A_{23}+A_3-A_{18}-A_{10}-A_{28}-A_{22}-A_{14}+A_6$	$A_{25}-A_3+A_{18}+A_{10}-A_{26}$	$A_{28}-A_{24}-A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}$	$A_{23}+A_{24}-A_{27}$	$A_{22}+A_{14}-A_6$	A49
A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$A_{50}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-A_{34}-A_{35}-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 12 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 composed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters S, L and R represents respectively the **magic** or **semi-magic** sums of orders 5, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.1. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.1. Let's consider following two **semi-magic** and magic square based on the Result 3.1:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												180	mgc	L=5*R/6												300
1063	-61	-64	-67	-70	-73	-76	-79	-82	-85	-88	-98	220	993	-51	-54	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	-48	300		
-91	5	11	43	14	17	29	32	-44	35	38	131	220	-81	5	11	78	14	17	29	32	-9	35	38	131	300		
-94	41	20	-22	23	28	65	41	2	44	-62	134	220	-84	41	20	-22	23	63	65	41	2	44	-27	134	300		
-97	-4	40	26	47	-19	17	-50	47	71	5	137	220	-87	-4	75	26	47	-19	17	-15	47	71	5	137	300		
-100	32	8	-1	13	38	53	35	20	-77	59	140	220	-90	32	8	-1	48	38	53	35	20	-42	59	140	300		
-103	16	11	44	-7	26	-74	32	65	17	50	143	220	-93	51	11	44	-7	26	-39	32	65	17	50	143	300		
-106	53	56	-140	59	62	77	80	-233	83	83	146	220	-96	53	56	-105	59	62	77	80	-198	83	83	146	300		
-109	89	65	26	68	-158	110	86	56	89	-251	149	220	-99	89	65	26	68	-123	110	86	56	89	-216	149	300		
-112	41	-146	71	95	29	68	-242	92	113	59	152	220	-102	41	-111	71	95	29	68	-207	92	113	59	152	300		
-14	77	59	44	-173	83	95	86	71	-263	101	54	220	46	77	59	44	-138	83	95	86	71	-228	101	4	300		
-115	-170	56	89	41	74	-260	80	104	68	98	155	220	-105	-135	56	89	41	74	-225	80	104	68	98	155	300		
98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	-1023	220	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	-943	300		
14a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	14b	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300		

(i) The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of the first example are $S_{5 \times 5} = 90$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 180$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 220$.

(ii) The **magic** sums of the second example are $S_{5 \times 5} = 125$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 250$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 300$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the condition given in (1).

Result 3.2. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62+A63-L	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	R-L-A59	R-L-A60	R-L-A61	R-L-A62	R-L-A63	11*L-9*R-A53
R-L-A64	$2*(L-S)/2-A51-A37-A44$	$2*A44+A51+A50+A37-A38-2*A31+(5*S-3*L)/2-A30$	A32	A33	A34	A35	$3*(L-S)/2-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36$	A36	$A38+2*A31-A37+A30-A44-A50$	A37	A64
R-L-A65	A30	A31	$(L-S)/2-A32$	$(L-S)/2-A33$	$(L-S)/2-A34$	$(L-S)/2-A35$	$A32+A33+A34+A35+A36-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A36$	$(3*S-L)/2-A30-A31-A38$	A38	A65
R-L-A66	$3*(L-S)/2-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29$	$A25+A26+A27+A28+A29-2*(L-S)/2$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15$	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	$(L-S)/2-A45$	A45	A66
R-L-A67	A25	$(L-S)/2-A25$	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	$(L-S)/2-A46$	A46	A67
R-L-A68	A26	$(L-S)/2-A26$	$A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16$	$S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	$S-L+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49$	$3*(L-S)/2-(A45+A46+A47+A48+A49)$	A68
R-L-A69	A27	$(L-S)/2-A27$	A1	$S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20$	$A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3$	A14	A18	A21	$(L-S)/2-A47$	A47	A69
R-L-A70	A28	$(L-S)/2-A28$	A2	A6	$S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8$	$A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S$	$S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14$	A22	$(L-S)/2-A48$	A48	A70
R-L-A71	A29	$(L-S)/2-A29$	A3	$A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S$	A10	$2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	A23	$(L-S)/2-A49$	A49	A71
$A72-A54-A55-2*A53+10*L-8*R-A63+A69+A70+A71+A67+A68+A64+A65+A66+A62-A61-A60-A59-A58-A57-A56$	$(5*S-3*L)/2+A51+A37-A30$	$(3*L-5*S)/2-A37+A30+A31-A44+A38$	$(L-S)/2-A39$	$A39+A40+A41+A42+A43-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A40$	$(L-S)/2-A41$	$(L-S)/2-A42$	$(L-S)/2-A43$	$A44+A37-A31$	$(3*S-L)/2-A37-A38-A51$	$A54-A72+A55+2*A53-11*L+9*R+A63-A69-A70-A71-A67-A68-A64-A65-A66+A62+A61+A60+A59+A58+A57+A56$
R-L-A72	A44	$(3*S-L)/2-A44-A51-A50$	A39	$3*(L-S)/2-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A50	A51	A72
A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A60	A61	A62	A63	$R-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62-A63$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with a **double-digit bordered magic square** of order 10 having a magic square of order 6 in the middle. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters S, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 6, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.2. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.2. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.2:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												180	mgc	L=5*R/6												276
	557	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-62	220		507	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-16	276
	-33	-79	85	41	42	43	44	-95	45	8	46	73	220		-27	-49	60	41	42	43	44	-50	45	8	46	73	276
	-34	39	40	-1	-2	-3	-4	135	-5	-66	47	74	220		-28	39	40	14	13	12	11	105	10	-61	47	74	276
	-35	-60	100	77	13	16	20	24	-50	-14	54	75	220		-29	-15	70	77	13	16	20	24	-30	1	54	75	276
	-36	34	6	-5	14	17	21	25	28	-15	55	76	220		-30	34	21	15	14	17	21	25	28	0	55	76	276
	-37	35	5	-5	10	18	22	26	29	200	-160	77	220		-31	35	20	-5	30	18	22	26	29	170	-115	77	276
	-38	36	4	10	-66	76	23	27	30	-16	56	78	220		-32	36	19	10	-46	76	23	27	30	-1	56	78	276
	-39	37	3	11	15	-46	153	-64	31	-17	57	79	220		-33	37	18	11	15	-26	133	-44	31	-2	57	79	276
	-40	38	2	12	114	19	-139	62	32	-18	58	80	220		-34	38	17	12	94	19	-99	62	32	-3	58	80	276
	-66	47	47	-8	170	-9	-10	-11	-12	59	-93	106	220		-14	22	72	7	140	6	5	4	3	59	-88	60	276
	-41	53	-112	48	-130	49	50	51	52	59	60	81	220		-35	53	-107	48	-85	49	50	51	52	59	60	81	276
	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-517	220		62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-461	276
23a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	23b	276	276	276	276	276	276	276	276	276	276	276	276	

(i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 180$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 220$.

(ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 230$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 276$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the condition given in (1).

Result 3.3. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48-L$	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	$11*L-9*R-A38$
R-L-A49	$L-2*M-A36-A22-A29$	$2*A29+A36+A35+A22-A23-2*A16-3*L/2+5*M-A15$	A17	A18	A19	A20	$3*L/2-3*M-A17-A18-A19-A20-A21$	A21	$A23+2*A16-A22+A15-A29-A35$	A22	A49
R-L-A50	A15	A16	$(L-2*M)/2-A17$	$(L-2*M)/2-A18$	$(L-2*M)/2-A19$	$(L-2*M)/2-A20$	$A17+A18+A19+A20+A21-L+2*M$	$(L-2*M)/2-A21$	$3*M-L/2-A15-A16-A23$	A23	A50
R-L-A51	$3*L/2-3*M-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$A10+A11+A12+A13+A14-L+2*M$	$2*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A7$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	$(L-2*M)/2-A30$	A30	A51
R-L-A52	A10	$(L-2*M)/2-A10$	$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2+A4-M/3$	$5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$	$(L-2*M)/2-A31$	A31	A52
R-L-A53	A11	$(L-2*M)/2-A11$	$2*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	A1	$2*M/3-A4$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A5$	$2*M-L+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34$	$3*L/2-3*M-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	A53
R-L-A54	A12	$(L-2*M)/2-A12$	A2	$M-A2-A3$	A3	A6	$M-A6-A7$	A7	$(L-2*M)/2-A32$	A32	A54
R-L-A55	A13	$(L-2*M)/2-A13$	$M-A2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4+A5-M$	$M-A3-A5$	$M-A6-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$	$(L-2*M)/2-A33$	A33	A55
R-L-A56	A14	$(L-2*M)/2-A14$	A4	$M-A4-A5$	A5	A8	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2*M/3-A1$	$(L-2*M)/2-A34$	A34	A56
$10*L-8*R+A57+A56+A55+A54+A53+A52+A51+A50+A49+A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-A39-2*A38$	$5*M-3*L/2+A36+A22-A15$	$3*L/2-5*M-A22+A15+A16-A29+A23$	$(L-2*M)/2-A24$	$A24+A25+A26+A27+A28-L+2*M$	$(L-2*M)/2-A25$	$(L-2*M)/2-A26$	$(L-2*M)/2-A27$	$(L-2*M)/2-A28$	$A29+A22-A16$	$3*M-L/2-A22-A23-A36$	$9*R-A57-A55-A56-A53-A54-A50-A51-A52+A48+A42+A39+A46+A47+A41+A43+A44+A45+A40-11*L-A49+2*A38$
R-L-A57	A29	$3*M-L/2-A29-A36-A35$	A24	$3*L/2-3*M-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	A25	A26	A27	A28	A35	A36	A57
A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	$R-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with a **double-digit bordered magic square** of order 10 having a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 6 composed of four equal sums **semi-magic squares** of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters M, S, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 3, 6, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.3. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.3. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.3:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											120	mgc	L=5*R/6											180
844	-36	-38	-40	-42	-44	-46	-48	-50	-52	-54	-154	240	884	-56	-58	-60	-62	-64	-66	-68	-70	-72	-74	-54	180
-56	-128	185	42	44	46	48	-125	50	-24	52	106	240	-76	-138	170	42	44	46	48	-140	50	-24	52	106	180
-58	38	40	-7	-9	-11	-13	160	-15	-47	54	108	240	-78	38	40	-12	-14	-16	-18	170	-20	-72	54	108	180
-60	-55	90	20	22	18	28	6	26	-33	68	110	240	-80	-70	100	10	27	8	18	11	16	-38	68	110	180
-62	28	7	24	4	32	8	40	12	-35	70	112	240	-82	28	2	29	-11	27	13	15	17	-40	70	112	180
-64	30	5	16	34	10	24	14	22	290	-255	114	240	-84	30	0	6	29	10	14	19	12	300	-270	114	180
-66	32	3	12	34	14	20	18	22	-37	72	116	240	-86	32	-2	12	19	14	20	3	22	-42	72	116	180
-68	34	1	32	0	28	16	36	8	-39	74	118	240	-88	34	-4	17	15	13	1	41	3	-44	74	118	180
-70	36	-1	16	26	18	24	6	30	-41	76	120	240	-90	36	-6	16	11	18	24	1	20	-46	76	120	180
-112	109	-1	-21	230	-23	-25	-27	-29	78	-101	162	240	-32	94	14	-26	240	-28	-30	-32	-34	78	-126	62	180
-72	66	-139	56	-195	58	60	62	64	78	80	122	240	-92	66	-164	56	-210	58	60	62	64	78	80	122	180
84	86	88	90	92	94	96	98	100	102	104	-794	240	84	86	88	90	92	94	96	98	100	102	104	-854	180
21a	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	21b	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 60$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 190$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 240$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 45$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 90$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 150$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 180$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the condition given in (1).

Result 3.4. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A_{42}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{45}+A_{46}+A_{47}+A_{48}+A_{49}+A_{50}+A_{51}+A_{52}-L$	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	$11*L-9*R-A_{42}$
R-L-A53	$2*(L-S)/2-A_{35}-A_{20}-A_{41}$	$2*A_{41}+A_{35}+A_{34}+A_{20}-A_{21}-2*A_{28}+L-5*(L-S)/2-A_{27}$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3*(L-S)/2-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}-A_{19}$	A19	$A_{21}+2*A_{28}-A_{20}+A_{27}-A_{41}-A_{34}$	A20	A53
R-L-A54	A27	A28	$(L-S)/2-A_{15}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{16}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{17}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{18}$	$A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}+A_{18}+A_{19}-L+S$	$(L-S)/2-A_{19}$	$L-A_{27}-A_{28}-3*(L-S)/2-A_{21}$	A21	A54
R-L-A55	$3*(L-S)/2-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{24}-A_{25}-A_{26}$	$A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{24}+A_{25}+A_{26}-2*(L-S)/2$	A1	$A_4+M-A_6-A_1$	$A_6-A_3-A_4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	$(L-S)/2-A_{29}$	A29	A55
R-L-A56	A22	$(L-S)/2-A_{22}$	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	$A_{10}+A_{11}+A_{12}-S+M$	$2*(S-M)-A_{10}-A_{11}-A_{12}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{30}$	A30	A56
R-L-A57	A23	$(L-S)/2-A_{23}$	$A_2+A_3-A_6$	$A_1+A_2-A_5$	M-A1-A2-A4	$A_4+A_5+A_6-A_2-A_3$	S-M-A11	A11	$A_{29}+A_{30}+A_3+1+A_{32}+A_{33}-L+S$	$3*(L-S)/2-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}$	A57
R-L-A58	A24	$(L-S)/2-A_{24}$	M-A1-A2-A3	$A_5-A_2-2*A_4+A_6$	$A_1+A_2+A_3+2*A_4-A_5-A_6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	$(L-S)/2-A_{31}$	A31	A58
R-L-A59	A25	$(L-S)/2-A_{25}$	S-M-A8	$2*S-A_8-A_1-3*A_4-2*A_{10}-A_{11}-A_{12}-M$	$2*A_8+A_1+A_9+3*A_4+2*A_{10}+A_{11}+A_{12}+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	$(S-M)/2$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A_{32}$	A32	A59
R-L-A60	A26	$(L-S)/2-A_{26}$	A8	$A_8+A_1+3*A_4+2*A_{10}+A_{11}+A_{12}-S$	$3*S-2*A_8-A_1-A_9-3*A_4-2*A_{10}-A_{11}-A_{12}-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(S-M)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A_{33}$	A33	A60
$10*L-8*R+A_{61}+A_{60}+A_{59}+A_{58}+A_{57}+A_{56}+A_{55}+A_{54}+A_{53}-A_{52}-A_{51}-A_{50}-A_{49}-A_{48}-A_{47}-A_{46}-A_{45}-A_{44}-A_{43}-2*A_{42}$	$L-5*(L-S)/2+A_{35}+A_{20}-A_{27}$	$5*(L-S)/2-L-A_{20}+A_{27}+A_{28}-A_{41}+A_{21}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{36}$	$A_{36}+A_{37}+A_3+8+A_{39}+A_{40}-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A_{37}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{38}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{39}$	$(L-S)/2-A_{40}$	$A_{41}+A_{20}-A_{28}$	$L-A_{20}-A_{21}-3*(L-S)/2-A_{35}$	$9*R-A_{61}-A_{59}-A_{60}-A_{57}-A_{58}-A_{54}-A_{55}-A_{56}+A_{52}+A_{46}+A_{43}+A_{50}+A_{51}+A_{45}+A_{47}+A_{48}+A_{49}+A_{44}-11*L-A_{53}+2*A_{42}$
R-L-A61	A41	$L-3*(L-S)/2-A_{41}-A_{35}-A_{34}$	A36	$3*(L-S)/2-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35	A61
A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	$R-A_{42}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{45}-A_{46}-A_{47}-A_{48}-A_{49}-A_{50}-A_{51}-A_{52}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **double-digit magic square** of order 10. The inner part is a **cornered magic square** of order 6 with magic square of order 4. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters M, S, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 4, 6, 10 and 12.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.4. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.4. Let's consider a following **semi-magic square** based on the Result 3.4:

8a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											240	8b	mgc	L=5*R/6											300
	457	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	18	200		377	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-2	300
	-33	-56	72	25	26	27	28	-30	29	19	30	63	200		-13	-26	77	25	26	27	28	15	29	19	30	63	300
	-34	37	38	10	9	8	7	65	6	-41	31	64	200		-14	37	38	25	24	23	22	35	21	-6	31	64	300
	-35	-65	100	11	67	-11	13	0	20	-4	39	65	200		-15	-20	70	11	67	-11	13	50	20	11	39	65	300
	-36	32	3	16	14	15	35	43	-23	-5	40	66	200		-16	32	18	16	14	15	35	-7	77	10	40	66	300
	-37	33	2	9	8	43	20	-1	21	135	-100	67	200		-17	33	17	9	8	43	20	49	21	105	-55	67	300
	-38	34	1	44	-9	33	12	-2	22	-6	41	68	200		-18	34	16	44	-9	33	12	48	22	9	41	68	300
	-39	35	0	2	-34	71	1	10	50	-7	42	69	200		-19	35	15	52	66	-29	51	35	-25	8	42	69	300
	-40	36	-1	18	54	-51	19	50	10	-8	43	70	200		-20	36	14	18	4	99	19	-25	35	7	43	70	300
	24	33	30	-11	170	-12	-13	-14	-15	43	-41	6	200		24	38	25	4	140	3	2	1	0	43	-6	26	300
	-41	51	-75	46	-135	47	48	49	50	44	45	71	200		-21	51	-40	46	-90	47	48	49	50	44	45	71	300
	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	-427	200		52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	-327	300
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 170$ and $R_{SM_{12 \times 12}} = 200$. Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$ and $MR_{2 \times 6} = 35 \times 105$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 150$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 250$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 300$. It is a *magic square* as it satisfies the conditions given in (??). Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 70 \times 140$ and $MR_{2 \times 6} = 50 \times 150$. It is a *magic square* as it satisfies the condition given in (1).

Result 3.5. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48-L	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	11*L-9*R-A38
R-L-A49	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	a18	T-S-A18	L-T-A30	A30	A49
R-L-A50	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	S-M-A11	A11	a19	T-S-A19	L-T-A31	A31	A50
R-L-A51	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	M-S+A10+A11+A12	2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12	A20	T-S-A20	L-T-A32	A32	A51
R-L-A52	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	3*(T-S)-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22	2*(S-T)+A18+A19+A20+A21+A22	L-T-A33	A33	A52
R-L-A53	2*S-3*M+A1-A8+3*A4-A11+A10	S-M-A8	3*M-2*S-A1+2*A8-3*A4+A11-A10+A9	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A21	T-S-A21	3*(T-L)+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36	4*(L-T)-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36	A53
R-L-A54	2*M-S-A1+A8-3*A4+A11-A10	A8	3*S-4*M+A1-2*A8+3*A4-A11+A10-A9	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A22	T-S-A22	L-T-A34	A34	A54
R-L-A55	A14	2*A11-T-5*S-A1+2*A9+2*A8+2*A12+A14-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M	A15	4*T+2*S-2*A14+A1-2*A11-2*A9-2*A8-2*A12+3*A4-A18+A19-8*M-A15-A16-A17	A16	A17	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A35	A35	A55
R-L-A56	T-S-A14	2*T+4*S+A1-2*A11-2*A9-2*A8-2*A12-A14+3*A4-A18+A19-8*M	T-S-A15	2*A14-3*S-3*T-A1+2*A11+2*A9+2*A8+2*A12-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M+A15+A16+A17	T-S-A16	T-S-A17	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A36	A36	A56
10*L-8*R+A57+A56+A55+A54+A53+A52+A51+A50+A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-A39-2*A38	2*L+6*T-6*S-2*A20-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9-A17-2*A8-A22-2*A12-A21-2*A14+3*A4-2*A18+A1-A24+A30-A31-3*M	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	6*S-4*L-4*T+2*A20+A29+A27+A16+2*A15+2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+A25+A28+A22+A26-A1+2*A12+A21+2*A14-3*A4+2*A18+2*A24-A30+A31+3*M	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	(L-T)/2	(9*T-7*L)/2	9*R-A57-A55-A56-A53-A54-A50-A51-A52+A48+A42+A39+A46+A47+A41+A43+A44+A45+A40-11*L-A49+2*A38
R-L-A57	6*S-L-7*T+2*A20+A16+2*A15+2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+A22+2*A12+A21+2*A14-3*A4+2*A18-A1+A24-A30+A31+3*M	A24	A25	A26	A27	5*L+3*T-6*S-2*A20-A29-A27-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9-A17-2*A8-A25-A28-A22-A26+A1-2*A12-A21-2*A14+3*A4-2*A18-2*A24+A30-A31-3*M	A28	A29	(9*T-7*L)/2	(L-T)/2	A57
A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	R-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **cornered magic squares** of orders 6, 8 and 10. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (1). The letters M, S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.5. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.5. Let's consider a following **semi-magic square** based on the Result 3.5:

7a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											240	7b	mgc	L=5*R/6											360
	413	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	22	200		283	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	12	360
	-29	11	67	-11	13	10	20	28	2	-10	40	59	200		1	11	137	-11	13	30	20	28	42	-10	40	59	360
	-30	16	14	15	35	9	21	29	1	-11	41	60	200		0	16	14	15	105	29	21	29	41	-11	41	60	360
	-31	9	8	43	20	33	-3	30	0	-12	42	61	200		-1	9	8	113	20	13	37	30	40	-12	42	61	360
	-32	44	-9	33	12	8	22	-60	90	-13	43	62	200		-2	114	-9	33	12	28	22	60	10	-13	43	62	360
	-33	14	12	23	11	15	35	31	-1	211	-181	63	200		-3	-16	32	53	31	25	75	31	39	211	-181	63	360
	-34	16	18	7	19	35	15	32	-2	-14	44	64	200		-4	66	18	-3	19	75	25	32	38	-14	44	64	360
	-35	24	80	25	-92	26	27	15	35	-15	45	65	200		-5	24	60	25	48	26	27	35	25	-15	45	65	360
	-36	6	-50	5	122	4	3	35	15	-16	46	66	200		-6	46	10	45	22	44	43	25	35	-16	46	66	360
	36	-192	-4	-5	-6	-7	351	-8	-9	15	35	-6	200		56	98	-4	-5	-6	-7	61	-8	-9	15	165	4	360
	-37	222	34	35	36	37	-321	38	39	35	15	67	200		-7	-68	34	35	36	37	-31	38	39	165	15	67	360
	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	-383	200		48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	-223	360
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 140$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 170$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 200$. Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$, $MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 150$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 200$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 270$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 300$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 360$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (??). Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 50 \times 100$, $MR_{2 \times 6} = 70 \times 210$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the condition given in (1).

Result 3.6. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59-A48	A69-A48-A50	A69-A48-A51	A69-A48-A52	A69-A48-A53	A69-A48-A54	A69-A48-A55	A69-A48-A56	A69-A48-A57	A69-A48-A58	A69-A48-A59	11*A48-9*A69-A49
A69-A48-A60	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15	A4	A7	A11	A15	A24-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	A34-A24-A29	A29	A48-A34-A41	A41	A60
A69-A48-A61	A24-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	A34-A24-A30	A30	A48-A34-A42	A42	A61
A69-A48-A62	A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16	A24-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3	A9	A13	A17	A20	A34-A24-A31	A31	A48-A34-A43	A43	A62
A69-A48-A63	A1	A24+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20	A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3	A14	A18	A21	A34-A24-A32	A32	A48-A34-A44	A44	A63
A69-A48-A64	A2	A6	A24+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8	A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-A24	A24-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14	A22	A34-A24-A33	A33	A48-A34-A45	A45	A64
A69-A48-A65	A3	A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-A24	A10	2*A24+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20	A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18	A23	2*A24-2*A34+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33	3*A34-3*A24-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33	A48-A34-A46	A46	A65
A69-A48-A66	A34-A24-A25	A30-A29-2*A9+A13-A25+2*A24-2*A21-A22-3*A23-A18-2*A19-3*A20-A14+A15+A16-2*A10+A2+A4+A11-A5+2*A6-A8+A3	A34-A24-A26	A34-A24-A27	A34-A24-A28	2*A25+A28+A27+A26-A30+A29+2*A9-A13-A34-A24+2*A21+A22+3*A23+A18+2*A19+3*A20+A14-A15-A16+2*A10-A2-A4-A11+A5-2*A6+A8-A3	(A34-A24)/2	(7*A24-5*A34)/2	A48-A34-A47	A47	A66
A69-A48-A67	A25	A29-A30+2*A9-A13+A34+A25-A11-3*A24+2*A21+A22+3*A23+A18+2*A19+3*A20+A14-A15-A16+2*A10-A2-A4+A5-2*A6+A8-A3	A26	A27	A28	A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-2*A9+A13+2*A34-2*A25-2*A21-A22-3*A23-A18-2*A19-3*A20-A14+A15+A16-2*A10+A2+A4+A11-A5+2*A6-A8+A3	(7*A24-5*A34)/2	(A34-A24)/2	3*A34-3*A48+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47	4*A48-4*A34-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47	A67
10*A48-8*A69+A68+A67+A66+A65+A64+A63+A62+A61+A60-A59-A58-A57-A56-A55-A54-A53-A52-A51-A50-2*A49	A48-A34-A35	A32+A34-A31+2*A24-A21-2*A22-2*A23-A26+A18-A19-A20-A14+2*A15+A16+A17-A41+A4+A42-A35+A27+A11+A7-A5-A9-2*A34	A48-A34-A36	A48-A34-A37	A48-A34-A38	A48-A34-A39	A48-A34-A40	A9+2*A34-A32+A34+A36+A31-2*A24+A21+2*A22+2*A23+A26-A18-A19+A20+A14-2*A15-A16-A17+A38+A39+A40+A37+A41-A4-A42+2*A35-2*A48-A27-A11-A7+A5	(A48-A34)/2	(9*A34-7*A48)/2	9*A69-11*A48-A68-A67-A66-A65-A64-A63-A62-A61-A60+A59+A53+A50+A57+A58+A52+A54+A55+A56+A51+2*A49
A69-A48-A68	A35	A9+2*A34-A32-2*A34+A31-2*A24+A21+2*A22+2*A23+A26-A18-A19+A20+A14-2*A15-A16-A17+A41-A4-A42+A35+A48-A27-A11-A7+A5	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A32-2*A34-A36-A31+2*A24-A21-2*A22-2*A23-A26+A18-A19-A20-A14+2*A15+A16+A17-A38-A39-A40-A37-A41+A4+A42-2*A35+3*A48+A27+A11+A7-A5-A9-2*A34	(9*A34-7*A48)/2	(A48-A34)/2	A68
A49	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A69-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **cornered magic square** of order 10, where in the upper-left part we have another **cornered magic square** of order 8, where the magic square of order 6 is in the upper-left corner. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic** or **semi-magic** sums of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.6. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.6. Let's consider following two **semi-magic** and **magic square** based on the Result 3.6:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												390	mgc	L=5*R/6												216
594	-40	-41	-42	-43	-44	-45	-46	-47	-48	-49	101	250	634	-34	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	-41	-42	-43	-33	216		
-50	88	24	27	31	35	-105	31	49	-21	61	80	250	-44	88	24	27	31	35	-145	11	49	-1	61	80	216		
-51	-60	25	28	32	36	39	30	50	-22	62	81	250	-45	-100	25	28	32	36	39	10	50	-2	62	81	216		
-52	6	-45	29	33	37	40	29	51	-23	63	82	250	-46	6	-85	29	33	37	40	9	51	-3	63	82	216		
-53	21	-121	87	34	38	41	28	52	-24	64	83	250	-47	21	-161	87	34	38	41	8	52	-4	64	83	216		
-54	22	26	-101	230	-119	42	27	53	-25	65	84	250	-48	22	26	-141	270	-159	42	7	53	-5	65	84	216		
-55	23	191	30	-260	73	43	95	-15	-26	66	85	250	-49	23	231	30	-340	73	43	135	-75	-6	66	85	216		
-56	35	-282	34	33	32	388	40	-100	-27	67	86	250	-50	15	-362	14	13	12	488	30	-90	-7	67	86	216		
-57	45	362	46	47	48	-308	-100	40	328	-288	87	250	-51	45	422	46	47	48	-428	-90	30	268	-208	87	216		
73	-15	-147	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	412	20	40	-43	250	-55	5	-167	4	3	2	1	0	392	30	-90	91	216		
-58	55	187	56	57	58	59	60	-372	40	20	88	250	-52	55	227	56	57	58	59	60	-332	-90	30	88	216		
69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	-564	250	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	-598	216		
13a	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	13b	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 180$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 220$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 250$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 80 \times 240$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 60$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 120$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 180$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 216$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 60 \times 180$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 60 \times 240$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the condition given in (1).

Result 3.7. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45-L$	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	$11*L-9*R-A35$
R-L-A46	$2*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A7$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	$T-2*M-A15$	A15	L-T-A27	A27	A46
R-L-A47	$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2+A4-M/3$	$5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$	$T-2*M-A16$	A16	L-T-A28	A28	A47
R-L-A48	$2*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	A1	$2*M/3-A4$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A5$	$T-2*M-A17$	A17	L-T-A29	A29	A48
R-L-A49	A2	M-A2-A3	A3	A6	M-A6-A7	A7	$T-2*M-A18$	A18	L-T-A30	A30	A49
R-L-A50	M-A2-A4	$A2+A3+A4+A5-M$	M-A3-A5	M-A6-A8	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$	$T-2*M-A19$	A19	L-T-A31	A31	A50
R-L-A51	A4	M-A4-A5	A5	A8	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2*M/3-A1$	$4*M-2*T+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19$	$3*T-6*M-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	L-T-A32	A32	A51
R-L-A52	$2*T-10*M/3-A10+A15-A16-2*A6-A7-A8$	$T-2*M-A10$	$T-2*M-A11$	$T-2*M-A12$	$T-2*M-A13$	$16*M/3-3*T+2*A10-A15+A16+2*A6+A7+A8+A11+A12+A13$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$(14*M-5*T)/2$	L-T-A33	A33	A52
R-L-A53	$A10-A15-T+4*M/3+A16+2*A6+A7+A8$	A10	A11	A12	A13	$4*T-22*M/3-2*A10+A15-A16-2*A6-A7-A8-A11-A12-A13$	$(14*M-5*T)/2$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$3*(T-L)+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33$	$4*(L-T)-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$	A53
$A54-8*R-A36+A52+A53+A49+A50+A51+A48-2*A35+10*L+A47+A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-A39-A38-A37$	$2*L-T+A27-A28+A17-(10/3)*M-A18-A7+2*A1-A8-A12-A21+A11$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	$3*T-4*L-A27+A28-A17+(10/3)*M+A18+A7-2*A1+A8+A12+2*A21-A11+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$A36-A54+9*R-A52-A53-A49-A50-A51-A48+2*A35-11*L-A47-A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40+A39+A38+A37$
R-L-A54	$A28-A17+(10/3)*M+A18+A7-2*A1+A8+A12+A21-A11-A27-L$	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	A26	$5*L-4*T+A27-A28+A17-(10/3)*M-A18-A7+2*A1-A8-A12+2*A21+A11-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$	A54
A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$R-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with a **cornered magic squares** of orders 8 and 10. It contains a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 6 at upper-left corner composed of four equal sums **semi-magic squares** of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (1). The letters M, S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.7. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.7. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.7:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											150	mgc	L=5*R/6											240
1197	-65	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	-83	-86	-89	-92	-162	250	1197	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	-96	-99	-102	-72	240
-95	7	37	4	19	13	16	12	52	-48	88	145	250	-105	15	33	12	27	9	24	-12	52	-48	88	145	240
-98	40	-26	34	16	10	22	9	55	-51	91	148	250	-108	36	-14	38	12	30	18	-15	55	-51	91	148	240
-101	1	37	10	13	25	10	6	58	-54	94	151	250	-111	9	41	10	21	21	18	-18	58	-54	94	151	240
-104	13	19	16	25	-5	28	3	61	-57	97	154	250	-114	13	31	16	25	7	28	-21	61	-57	97	154	240
-107	16	22	10	-8	58	-2	0	64	-60	100	157	250	-117	28	10	22	4	54	2	-24	64	-60	100	157	240
-110	19	7	22	31	-5	22	162	-98	-63	103	160	250	-120	19	19	22	31	-1	30	210	-170	-63	103	160	240
-113	11	27	24	21	18	91	32	-64	-66	106	163	250	-123	-29	3	0	-3	-6	155	20	20	-66	106	163	240
-116	53	37	40	43	46	-27	-64	32	559	-519	166	250	-126	69	37	40	43	46	-115	20	20	559	-519	166	240
-96	-38	-30	-33	-36	-39	-42	-45	423	20	20	146	250	-16	-78	-30	-33	-36	-39	-42	-45	463	20	20	56	240
-119	78	70	73	76	79	82	85	-383	20	20	169	250	-129	118	70	73	76	79	82	85	-423	20	20	169	240
112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136	139	142	-1147	250	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136	139	142	-1157	240
20a	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	20b	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 48$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 96$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 200$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 250$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 64 \times 192$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 60$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 100$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the conditions given in (1).

Result 3.8. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A_{41}+A_{42}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{45}+A_{46}+A_{47}+A_{48}+A_{49}+A_{50}+A_{51}-L$	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	$11*L-9*R-A_{41}$
R-L-A52	A18	A19	$2*(T-S)/2-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}$	A15	A16	A17	$2*S-T+A_{18}-A_{19}+A_{23}$	$2*(T-S)/2-A_{23}-2*A_{18}$	L-T-A28	A28	A52
R-L-A53	$2*A_{13}+A_{24}+A_{14}+2*A_{18}-2*(T-S)/2-A_{19}$	$2*(T-S)/2-2*A_{18}-A_{13}$	$A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A_{15}$	$(T-S)/2-A_{16}$	$(T-S)/2-A_{17}$	$2*(T-S)/2-A_{23}-A_{13}-A_{24}-A_{18}+A_{19}$	$2*S-T+A_{18}+A_{23}-A_{14}$	L-T-A29	A29	A53
R-L-A54	$2*(T-S)/2-A_7-A_8-A_9$	$A_7+A_8+A_9-(T-S)/2$	A1	$A_4+S-A_6-A_1$	$A_6-A_3-A_4$	A3	$A_{10}+A_{11}+A_{12}-(T-S)/2$	$2*(T-S)/2-A_{10}-A_{11}-A_{12}$	$A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+A_{34}+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-A_{34}-4*T$	A54
R-L-A55	A7	$(T-S)/2-A_7$	A6	A4	A5	$S-A_4-A_5-A_6$	$(T-S)/2-A_{10}$	A10	L-T-A30	A30	A55
R-L-A56	A8	$(T-S)/2-A_8$	$A_2+A_3-A_6$	$A_1+A_2-A_5$	$S-A_1-A_2-A_4$	$A_4+A_5+A_6-A_2-A_3$	$(T-S)/2-A_{11}$	A11	L-T-A31	A31	A56
R-L-A57	A9	$(T-S)/2-A_9$	$S-A_1-A_2-A_3$	$A_5-A_2-2*A_4+A_6$	$A_1+A_2+A_3+2*A_4-A_5-A_6$	A2	$(T-S)/2-A_{12}$	A12	L-T-A32	A32	A57
R-L-A58	$T-2*A_{13}-A_{14}+A_{19}-3*A_{18}-A_{23}-A_{24}$	$A_{23}+3*A_{18}+A_{24}-A_{19}+A_{13}-2*(T-S)/2$	$A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A_{20}$	$(T-S)/2-A_{21}$	$(T-S)/2-A_{22}$	A13	A14	L-T-A33	A33	A58
R-L-A59	A23	$T-A_{23}-A_{18}-2*(T-S)/2-A_{24}$	$2*(T-S)/2-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18	L-T-A34	A34	A59
$10*L-8*R+A_{60}+A_{59}+A_{58}+A_{57}+A_{56}+A_{55}+A_{54}+A_{53}+A_{52}-A_{51}-A_{50}-A_{49}-A_{48}-A_{47}-A_{46}-A_{45}-A_{44}-A_{43}-A_{42}-2*A_{41}$	L-T-A35	$T-A_1+A_{29}-A_{28}+A_{11}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{20}-6*(T-S)/2-A_{35}+2*A_{10}+A_{12}-3*A_4$	$T+A_1-A_{29}+A_{28}-A_{11}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{20}+6*(T-S)/2+2*A_{35}-2*A_{10}-A_{12}-2*L+3*A_4+A_{36}+A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{39}+A_{40}$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$9*R-11*L-A_{60}-A_{59}-A_{58}-A_{57}-A_{56}-A_{55}-A_{54}-A_{53}-A_{52}+A_{51}+A_{50}+A_{49}+A_{48}+A_{47}+A_{46}+A_{45}+A_{44}+A_{43}+A_{42}+2*A_{41}$
R-L-A60	A35	$A_1-A_{29}+A_{28}-A_{11}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{20}+6*(T-S)/2+A_{35}-2*T-2*A_{10}-A_{12}+L+3*A_4$	$3*L-2*T-A_1+A_{29}-A_{28}+A_{11}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{20}-6*(T-S)/2-2*A_{35}+2*A_{10}+A_{12}-3*A_4-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2	A60
A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	$R-A_{41}-A_{42}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{45}-A_{46}-A_{47}-A_{48}-A_{49}-A_{50}-A_{51}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **cornered magic square** of order 10, where in the left upper part we have a **double-digit bordered magic square** of order 8 having magic square of order 4 at the center of it. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters M, S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic** or **semi-magic** sums of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.8. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.8. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 3.8:

10a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											120	10b	mgc	L=5*R/6											360
	456	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-91	200		316	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	9	360
	-22	28	29	-18	25	26	27	22	-29	12	38	62	200		-2	28	29	2	25	26	27	102	-9	32	38	62	360
	-23	71	-19	48	5	4	3	-29	27	11	39	63	200		-3	51	1	38	15	14	13	-9	107	31	39	63	360
	-24	6	24	11	37	-11	13	33	-3	137	-87	64	200		-4	26	14	11	137	-11	13	23	17	77	-7	64	360
	-25	17	13	16	14	15	5	10	20	10	40	65	200		-5	17	23	16	14	15	105	20	20	30	40	65	360
	-26	18	12	9	8	13	20	9	21	9	41	66	200		-6	18	22	9	8	113	20	19	21	29	41	66	360
	-27	19	11	14	-9	33	12	8	22	8	42	67	200		-7	19	21	114	-9	33	12	18	22	28	42	67	360
	-28	-82	85	63	0	-1	-2	23	24	7	43	68	200		-8	38	65	53	10	9	8	23	24	27	43	68	360
	-29	33	-45	-33	30	31	32	34	28	6	44	69	200		-9	33	55	-13	30	31	32	34	28	26	44	69	360
	-73	5	39	146	4	3	2	1	0	25	-65	113	200		47	25	99	46	24	23	22	21	20	35	-15	13	360
	-30	45	11	-96	46	47	48	49	50	-65	25	70	200		-10	45	-29	24	46	47	48	49	50	-15	35	70	360
	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-416	200		51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-256	360
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 50$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 110$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 160$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 200$. Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 50 \times 200$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 230$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 300$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 360$. We get it a *magic square* by applying the condition given in (1). Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 70 \times 280$.

Result 3.9. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$A_{27}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+A_{34}+A_{35}+A_{36}+A_{37}-L$	R-L-A28	R-L-A29	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	$11*L-9*R-A_{27}$
R-L-A38	$A_1-A_3-A_5-A_6-A_8+A_7$	$A_6+A_8-2*m+A_{11}+A_1-A_3-A_5$	$2*m$	$2*m+2*A_3+2*A_5-A_7-A_{11}-2*A_1$	$A_5+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}+A_{10}-A_9$	$2*m-A_9-A_5-A_{10}$	$A_9-2*A_3+A_7+A_{11}$	A_9	$L-4*m-A_{19}$	A_{19}	A_{38}
R-L-A39	$m+A_3+A_5+A_6+A_8-A_7-A_1$	$3*m+A_3+A_5-A_6-A_8-A_{11}-A_1$	$(-m)$	$A_7-m+A_{11}+2*A_1-2*A_3-2*A_5$	$m+A_9-A_{10}+A_{11}-A_5-2*A_3+A_7$	$A_9+A_5+A_{10}-m$	$m-A_9+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	$m-A_9$	$L-4*m-A_{20}$	A_{20}	A_{39}
R-L-A40	$2*A_3+2*A_5-A_7-A_{11}-A_1$	A_1	$A_6+A_8+A_{11}-A_3-A_5$	$2*m+A_7-A_3-A_5-A_6-A_8$	$A_5+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	A_5	$2*m+A_7+A_{11}-A_{10}-2*A_3-2*A_5$	A_{10}	$L-4*m-A_{21}$	A_{21}	A_{40}
R-L-A41	$A_1+m-2*A_3-2*A_5+A_7+A_{11}$	$m-A_1$	$m+A_3+A_5-A_6-A_8-A_{11}$	$A_3+A_5+A_6+A_8-A_7-m$	$m+A_7+A_{11}-A_5-2*A_3$	$m-A_5$	$2*A_3+2*A_5-A_7-A_{11}+A_{10}-m$	$m-A_{10}$	$L-4*m-A_{22}$	A_{22}	A_{41}
R-L-A42	$A_3+A_2-A_7-A_{11}+A_4$	$2*m-A_3-A_2-A_4$	$A_7+A_{11}-A_3$	A_3	$2*m-A_6-A_8-A_{11}$	$A_6+A_8-A_7$	A_7	A_{11}	$L-4*m-A_{23}$	A_{23}	A_{42}
R-L-A43	$m+A_7+A_{11}-A_4-A_3-A_2$	$A_3+A_2+A_4-m$	$m+A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	$m-A_3$	$A_6+A_8+A_{11}-m$	$m+A_7-A_6-A_8$	$m-A_7$	$m-A_{11}$	$L-4*m-A_{24}$	A_{24}	A_{43}
R-L-A44	$A_2+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	A_2	$2*m+A_7+A_{11}-2*A_2-A_4-2*A_3$	A_4	$A_6+A_{11}-A_7$	A_6	A_8	$2*m+A_7-2*A_6-A_8-A_{11}$	$L-4*m-A_{25}$	A_{25}	A_{44}
R-L-A45	$m+A_7+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3$	$m-A_2$	$2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}+2*A_2+A_4-m$	$m-A_4$	$m+A_7-A_{11}-A_6$	$m-A_6$	$m-A_8$	$2*A_6+A_8+A_{11}-A_7-m$	$12*m-3*L+A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{24}+A_{25}$	$4*L-16*m-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{24}-A_{25}$	A_{45}
$10*L-8*R-A_{28}+A_{46}+A_{45}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{42}+A_{40}+A_{41}+A_{39}+A_{38}-A_{34}-A_{35}-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-2*A_{27}-A_{29}-A_{30}$	$L-4*m-A_{13}$	$7*m-A_{19}+A_{11}-A_{13}+A_{20}-2*A_4-2*A_6-2*A_8+3*A_7-4*A_3-2*A_5-2*A_{10}-2*A_2$	$L-4*m-A_{14}$	$L-4*m-A_{15}$	$L-4*m-A_{16}$	$L-4*m-A_{17}$	$L-4*m-A_{18}$	$m-2*L+2*A_{13}+A_{19}-A_{11}-A_{20}+2*A_4+2*A_6+2*A_8-3*A_7+4*A_3+2*A_5+2*A_{10}+2*A_2+A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}+A_{18}$	$(L-4*m)/2$	$(9*4*m-7*L)/2$	$9*R-11*L+A_{28}-A_{46}-A_{45}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{42}-A_{40}-A_{41}-A_{39}-A_{38}+A_{34}+A_{35}+A_{36}+A_{37}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+2*A_{27}+A_{29}+A_{30}$
R-L-A46	A_{13}	$A_{19}-A_{11}+A_{13}-A_{20}+2*A_4+2*A_6+2*A_8-3*A_7+4*A_3+2*A_5+2*A_{10}+2*A_2-11*m+L$	A_{14}	A_{15}	A_{16}	A_{17}	A_{18}	$3*L-5*m-2*A_{13}-A_{19}+A_{11}+A_{20}-2*A_4-2*A_6-2*A_8+3*A_7-4*A_3-2*A_5-2*A_{10}-2*A_2-A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	$(9*4*m-7*L)/2$	$(L-4*m)/2$	A_{46}
A_{27}	A_{28}	A_{29}	A_{30}	A_{31}	A_{32}	A_{33}	A_{34}	A_{35}	A_{36}	A_{37}	$R-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-A_{34}-A_{35}-A_{36}-A_{37}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **cornered magic square** of order 10, where in the left upper part we have a **striped pandiagonal magic square** of order 8. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters T, L and R represents respectively the **magic** or **semi-magic** sums of orders 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.9. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.9. Let's consider following two **semi-magic** and **magic square** based on the Result 3.8:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											180	mgc	L=5*R/6											240
623	-25	-27	-29	-31	-33	-35	-37	-39	-41	-43	-63	220	603	-25	-27	-29	-31	-33	-35	-37	-39	-41	-43	-23	240
-45	-46	14	40	32	-3	-35	51	27	53	47	85	220	-45	-46	-6	60	52	-3	-15	51	27	33	47	85	240
-47	66	6	-20	-12	23	55	-31	-7	51	49	87	220	-47	76	36	-30	-22	33	45	-21	3	31	49	87	240
-49	3	11	43	-17	-5	19	-3	29	49	51	89	220	-49	3	11	43	3	-5	19	17	29	29	51	89	240
-51	17	9	-23	37	25	1	23	-9	47	53	91	220	-51	27	19	-13	27	35	11	13	1	27	53	91	240
-53	-9	-5	39	15	-37	23	23	31	45	55	93	220	-53	-9	15	39	15	-17	23	23	31	25	55	93	240
-55	29	25	-19	5	57	-3	-3	-11	43	57	95	220	-55	39	15	-9	15	47	7	7	-1	23	57	95	240
-57	-11	13	21	17	29	21	25	-35	41	59	97	220	-57	-11	13	41	17	29	21	25	-15	21	59	97	240
-59	31	7	-1	3	-9	-1	-5	55	71	29	99	220	-59	41	17	-11	13	1	9	5	45	131	-51	99	240
11	65	-101	63	61	59	57	55	141	50	-270	29	220	51	45	-31	43	41	39	37	35	111	40	-160	-11	240
-61	35	201	37	39	41	43	45	-41	-270	50	101	220	-61	35	111	37	39	41	43	45	-31	-160	40	101	240
63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	-583	220	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	-563	240
11a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	11b	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $T_{8 \times 8} = 80$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 180$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 220$. Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 100 \times 400$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $T_{8 \times 8} = 120$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. Moreover, in this case the *magic rectangles sums* are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 80 \times 320$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the condition given in (1).

Result 3.10. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$A_{41}+A_{42}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{45}+A_{46}+A_{47}+A_{48}+A_{49}+A_{50}+A_{51}-A_{32}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{42}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{43}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{44}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{45}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{46}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{47}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{48}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{49}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{50}$	$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{51}$	$11*A_{32}-9*A_{61}-A_{41}$
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{52}$	$2*A_{18}-2*A_4-2*A_7-A_{12}+A_3+A_6$	$3*A_4+3*A_7-A_{15}-A_2+A_{12}-A_3-A_6-2*A_{18}$	$A_2+A_{14}-A_{16}-4*A_4-4*A_7+A_3+A_6-A_1+4*A_{18}+A_{15}$	$A_{16}+3*A_4-3*A_{18}+3*A_7-A_3-A_6+A_1-A_{14}$	A_3	$2*A_{18}-A_9-A_4-A_7-A_5-A_3$	$A_5+A_8-A_{16}+A_3+A_6-A_1+A_9$	$A_{16}+A_4+A_7-A_3-A_6+A_1-A_8-A_{18}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{25}$	A_{25}	A_{52}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{53}$	A_2	$A_4+A_7-A_{15}-A_{18}$	A_1	$2*A_{18}-A_4-A_7+A_{15}-A_1-A_2$	A_5	$A_{18}-A_9-A_4-A_7$	$A_{16}+2*A_4-2*A_{18}+2*A_7+A_1-A_{10}$	$A_9-A_4-A_7+2*A_{18}-A_{16}-A_1+A_{10}-A_5$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{26}$	A_{26}	A_{53}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{54}$	$2*A_4+2*A_7-A_{13}-A_{18}-A_{14}+A_{16}-A_3-A_6+A_1-A_2$	$4*A_{18}-3*A_4-3*A_7-A_{12}+A_3+A_6-A_{13}-A_1$	$2*A_4+2*A_7+A_1-2-A_3-A_6+A_{13}+A_{15}-2*A_{18}$	$A_2+A_{13}+A_{14}-A_{16}-A_4-A_7+A_3+A_6-A_{15}$	$2*A_4-A_{18}-A_8+A_{16}+A_7-A_3-A_6+A_1-A_5$	$A_3-A_4+2*A_{18}-A_{16}-2*A_7-A_1+A_{10}$	$A_9+A_7-A_3$	$A_8+A_3+A_6-A_{10}+A_5-A_9-A_4$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{27}$	A_{27}	A_{54}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{55}$	$A_{12}+A_{13}+A_{14}-A_{16}-A_1$	$A_1-A_4-A_7+A_{13}+2*A_{15}+A_2$	$2*A_4+2*A_7-A_{12}-A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{18}+A_{16}-2*A_{15}-A_2$	$2*A_{18}-A_4-A_7-A_{13}$	$2*A_{18}-2*A_4+A_8-A_{16}-A_7+A_6-A_1$	$A_{16}+3*A_4-4*A_{18}+4*A_7+A_1+2*A_9+A_5-A_{10}$	$3*A_{18}-A_8-3*A_7-A_6-2*A_9+A_{10}-A_5-2*A_4$	A_4	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{28}$	A_{28}	A_{55}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{56}$	A_6	$A_9+A_{18}-A_{11}-A_6$	$A_{11}-A_8-A_9$	A_8	A_{12}	$A_{15}+A_{18}-A_{17}-A_{12}$	$A_{17}-A_{14}-A_{15}$	A_{14}	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{29}$	A_{29}	A_{56}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{57}$	A_{11}	A_9	A_{10}	$A_{18}-A_9-A_{10}-A_{11}$	A_{17}	A_{15}	A_{16}	$A_{18}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{30}$	A_{30}	A_{57}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{58}$	$A_7+A_8-A_{11}$	$A_6+A_7-A_{10}$	$A_{18}-A_6-A_7-A_9$	$A_9+A_{10}+A_{11}-A_7-A_8$	$A_{13}+A_{14}-A_{17}$	$A_{12}+A_{13}-A_{16}$	$A_{18}-A_{12}-A_{13}-A_{15}$	$A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{31}$	A_{31}	A_{58}
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{59}$	$A_{18}-A_6-A_7-A_8$	$A_{10}-A_7-2*A_9+A_{11}$	$A_6+A_7+A_8+2*A_9-A_{10}-A_{11}$	A_7	$A_{18}-A_{12}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$A_{16}-A_{13}-2*A_{15}+A_{17}$	$A_{12}+A_{13}+A_{14}+2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}$	A_{13}	$6*A_{18}-3*A_{32}+A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}$	$4*A_{32}-8*A_{18}-A_{25}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}$	A_{59}
$10*A_{32}-8*A_{61}+A_{60}+A_{59}+A_{58}+A_{57}+A_{56}+A_{55}+A_{54}+A_{53}+A_{52}-A_{51}-A_{50}-A_{49}-A_{48}-A_{47}-A_{46}-A_{45}-A_{44}-A_{43}-A_{42}-2*A_{41}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{19}$	$3*A_4+A_{26}-A_{19}+A_{12}+3*A_7-A_6-A_3-2*A_{18}-A_{15}-A_{25}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{20}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{21}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{22}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{23}$	$A_{32}-2*A_{18}-A_{24}$	$6*A_{18}-2*A_{32}+2*A_{19}+A_{15}+A_{25}-3*A_4-A_{26}-A_{12}-3*A_7+A_6+A_3+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{24}$	$(A_{32}-2*A_{18})/2$	$(9*2*A_{18}-7*A_{32})/2$	$9*A_{61}-11*A_{32}-A_{60}-A_{59}-A_{58}-A_{57}-A_{56}-A_{55}-A_{54}-A_{53}-A_{52}+A_{51}+A_{50}+A_{49}+A_{48}+A_{47}+A_{46}+A_{45}+A_{44}+A_{43}+A_{42}+2*A_{41}$
$A_{61}-A_{32}-A_{60}$	A_{19}	$A_{15}+A_{25}-3*A_4-A_{26}+A_{19}+A_{32}-A_{12}-3*A_7+A_6+A_3$	A_{20}	A_{21}	A_{22}	A_{23}	A_{24}	$3*A_{32}-8*A_{18}-2*A_{19}-A_{15}-A_{25}+3*A_4+A_{26}+A_{12}+3*A_7-A_6-A_3-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{24}$	$(9*2*A_{18}-7*A_{32})/2$	$(A_{32}-2*A_{18})/2$	A_{60}
A_{41}	A_{42}	A_{43}	A_{44}	A_{45}	A_{46}	A_{47}	A_{48}	A_{49}	A_{50}	A_{51}	$A_{61}-A_{41}-A_{42}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{45}-A_{46}-A_{47}-A_{48}-A_{49}-A_{50}-A_{51}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **cornered magic square** of order 10, where in the upper-left part we have a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 8 composed by four equal sums magic squares of order 4. In order to bring it a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.10. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.10. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.8:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												-60	mgc	L=5*R/6												300
1122	-30	-33	-36	-39	-42	-45	-48	-51	-54	-57	-387	300	1092	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-57	300		
-60	61	-79	217	-119	17	36	66	-39	-23	83	140	300	-90	61	-79	217	-119	17	36	66	-39	7	83	140	300		
-63	14	-84	11	139	23	-4	-33	94	-26	86	143	300	-93	14	-84	11	139	23	-4	-33	94	4	86	143	300		
-66	-69	114	39	-4	-42	70	47	5	-29	89	146	300	-96	-69	114	39	-4	-42	70	47	5	1	89	146	300		
-69	74	129	-187	64	82	-22	0	20	-32	92	149	300	-99	74	129	-187	64	82	-22	0	20	-2	92	149	300		
-72	26	48	-26	32	44	30	-44	50	-35	95	152	300	-102	26	48	-26	32	44	30	-44	50	-5	95	152	300		
-75	41	35	38	-34	59	53	56	-88	-38	98	155	300	-105	41	35	38	-34	59	53	56	-88	-8	98	155	300		
-78	20	17	-10	53	38	35	-64	71	-41	101	158	300	-108	20	17	-10	53	38	35	-64	71	-11	101	158	300		
-81	-7	-20	78	29	-61	-38	132	47	464	-404	161	300	-111	-7	-20	78	29	-61	-38	132	47	374	-284	161	300		
-281	-5	-127	-8	-11	-14	-17	-20	442	30	-50	361	300	19	25	-127	22	19	16	13	10	382	45	-155	31	300		
-84	65	187	68	71	74	77	80	-382	-50	30	164	300	-114	65	217	68	71	74	77	80	-292	-155	45	164	300		
107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137	-1042	300	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137	-1042	300		
12a	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	12b	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 220$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 300$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 8} = 60 \times 240$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 250$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 300$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 8} = 90 \times 360$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the condition given in (1).

Result 3.11. Let's consider following magic squares of order 12 with reduced entries:

(R-T)/2-A60	A62	(R-T)/2-A53	(R-T)/2-A54	(R-T)/2-A55	(R-T)/2-A56	$3*(T-R)/2+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59$	(R-T)/2-A57	(R-T)/2-A58	(R-T)/2-A59	$3*T-2*R+A52-A62+A60$	(R-T)/2-A52
A61	A60	A53	A54	A55	A56	$2*(R-T)-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59$	A57	A58	A59	A52	$2*T-R-A61-A60-A52$
(R-T)/2-A63	A63	T-S-A28	$2*T+3*S+A30-A25-A31$	T-S-A25	$A29+2*A28-7*T+2*S+A27+A26+2*A25+A32+A33+A35+2*A31+A34$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A29	$T-A32-A33-A35-A31-A34-A28-A30$	A45	(R-T)/2-A45
(R-T)/2-A64	A64	T-S-A31	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15$	A4	A7	A11	A15	$S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A31	A46	(R-T)/2-A46
(R-T)/2-A65	A65	T-S-A32	$S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19$	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	A32	A47	(R-T)/2-A47
(R-T)/2-A66	A66	T-S-A33	$A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16$	$S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	A33	A48	(R-T)/2-A48
$3*(T-R)/2+A63+A64+A65+A66+A67+A68+A69$	$2*(R-T)-A63-A64-A65-A66-A67-A68-A69$	T-S-A34	A1	$S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20$	$A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3$	A14	A18	A21	A34	$2*(R-T)-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51$	$3*(T-R)/2+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51$
(R-T)/2-A67	A67	T-S-A35	A2	A6	$S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8$	$A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S$	$S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14$	A22	A35	A49	(R-T)/2-A49
(R-T)/2-A68	A68	T-S-A30	A3	$A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S$	A10	$2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	A23	A30	A50	(R-T)/2-A50
(R-T)/2-A69	A69	$A28+A30+7*S+A32+A33+A35+A31+A34-6*T$	$A25+A31-T-A30-4*S$	A25	$8*T-A29-2*A28-3*S-A27-A26-2*A25-A32-A33-A35-2*A31-A34$	A26	A27	A29	A28	A51	(R-T)/2-A51
$2*T-R-A52-A44-A61$	$R-T-A52-A60-A44$	A37	A38	A39	A40	$2*(R-T)-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	A41	A42	A43	A44	$T-R+2*A52+A60+A44+A61$
$(T-R)/2+A52+A60+A44$	$3*T-2*R+A52+A44-A62$	(R-T)/2-A37	(R-T)/2-A38	(R-T)/2-A39	(R-T)/2-A40	$3*(T-R)/2+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43$	(R-T)/2-A41	(R-T)/2-A42	(R-T)/2-A43	$R-T-2*A52+A62-A60-A44$	(R-T)/2-A44

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered semi-magic square** embedded with **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 8. The inner block is a magic square of order 6. It becomes **semi-magic** only due to order 8 being a **semi-magic**. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (3).

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.11. First example is of **semi-magic** square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (3).

Example 3.11. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 3.11:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												60	mgc	S=3*T/4												240
-99	133	-85	-87	-89	-91	757	-93	-95	-97	149	-83	220	-109	133	-95	-97	-99	-101	787	-103	-105	-107	229	-93	240		
131	129	115	117	119	121	-727	123	125	127	113	-273	220	131	129	115	117	119	121	-767	123	125	127	113	-213	240		
-105	135	-5	559	1	-35	-1	-3	-7	-349	99	-69	220	-115	135	-15	789	-9	-215	-11	-13	-17	-309	99	-79	240		
-107	137	-11	145	17	23	31	39	-155	71	101	-71	220	-117	137	-21	145	17	23	31	39	-105	71	101	-81	240		
-109	139	-13	-65	19	25	33	41	47	73	103	-73	220	-119	139	-23	-15	19	25	33	41	47	73	103	-83	240		
-111	141	-15	-19	-35	27	35	43	49	75	105	-75	220	-121	141	-25	-19	15	27	35	43	49	75	105	-85	240		
897	-867	-17	11	-187	143	37	45	51	77	-615	645	220	927	-907	-27	11	-137	143	37	45	51	77	-655	675	240		
-113	143	-19	13	21	-147	343	-183	53	79	107	-77	220	-123	143	-29	13	21	-97	293	-133	53	79	107	-87	240		
-115	145	-9	15	265	29	-379	115	55	69	109	-79	220	-125	145	-19	15	215	29	-279	115	55	69	109	-89	240		
-117	147	249	-499	59	95	61	63	67	65	111	-81	220	-127	147	359	-739	59	265	61	63	67	65	111	-91	240		
-241	-279	83	85	87	89	-503	91	93	95	97	523	220	-181	-299	83	85	87	89	-543	91	93	95	97	543	240		
309	117	-53	-55	-57	-59	533	-61	-63	-65	-259	-67	220	319	197	-63	-65	-67	-69	563	-71	-73	-75	-279	-77	240		
24a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	24b	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240		

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 160$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 220$. The magic magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. The magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 8} = 20 \times 80$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the condition given in (3).

Result 3.12. Let's consider following magic squares of order 12 with reduced entries:

(R-T)/2-A45	A47	(R-T)/2-A38	(R-T)/2-A39	(R-T)/2-A40	(R-T)/2-A41	$3*(T-R)/2+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44$	(R-T)/2-A42	(R-T)/2-A43	(R-T)/2-A44	$3*T-2*R+A37-A47+A45$	(R-T)/2-A37
A46	A45	A38	A39	A40	A41	$2*(R-T)-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44$	A42	A43	A44	A37	$2*T-R-A46-A45-A37$
(R-T)/2-A48	A48	T-2*M-T	$12*M-6*T+A10+A11+A12+A13+A14+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19+A20+2*T$	T-2*M-A16	T-2*M-A17	T-2*M-A18	T-2*M-A19	T-2*M-A20	$T-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14-A15-T$	A30	(R-T)/2-A30
(R-T)/2-A49	A49	T-2*M-A10	$2*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A7$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	A10	A31	(R-T)/2-A31
(R-T)/2-A50	A50	T-2*M-A11	$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2+A4-M/3$	$5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$	A11	A32	(R-T)/2-A32
(R-T)/2-A51	A51	T-2*M-A12	$2*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	A1	$2*M/3-A4$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A5$	A12	A33	(R-T)/2-A33
$3*(T-R)/2+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54$	$2*(R-T)-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54$	T-2*M-A13	A2	M-A2-A3	A3	A6	M-A6-A7	A7	A13	$2*(R-T)-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36$	$3*(T-R)/2+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36$
(R-T)/2-A52	A52	T-2*M-A14	M-A2-A4	$A2+A3+A4+A5-M$	M-A3-A5	M-A6-A8	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$	A14	A34	(R-T)/2-A34
(R-T)/2-A53	A53	T-2*M-A15	A4	M-A4-A5	A5	A8	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2*M/3-A1$	A15	A35	(R-T)/2-A35
(R-T)/2-A54	A54	$14*M-6*T+A10+A11+A12+A13+A14+A15+T$	$7*(T-2*M)-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-2*T$	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	T	A36	(R-T)/2-A36
$2*T-R-A37-A29-A46$	R-T-A37-A45-A29	A22	A23	A24	A25	$2*(R-T)-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	A26	A27	A28	A29	$T-R+2*A37+A45+A29+A46$
$(T-R)/2+A37+A45+A29$	$3*T-2*R+A37+A29-A47$	(R-T)/2-A22	(R-T)/2-A23	(R-T)/2-A24	(R-T)/2-A25	$3*(T-R)/2+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$	(R-T)/2-A26	(R-T)/2-A27	(R-T)/2-A28	$R-T-2*A37+A47-A45-A29$	(R-T)/2-A29

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered semi-magic square** embedded with **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 8. The inner block is a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 6 composed with four equal sums **semi-magic squares** of order 3. It becomes **semi-magic** only due to order 8 being a **semi-magic**. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (3).

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.12. First example is of **semi-magic square** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (3).

Example 3.12. Let's consider a following **semi-magic square** based on the Result 3.12:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												60	mgc	S=3*T/4												240
-99	133	-85	-87	-89	-91	757	-93	-95	-97	149	-83	220	-109	133	-95	-97	-99	-101	787	-103	-105	-107	229	-93	240		
131	129	115	117	119	121	-727	123	125	127	113	-273	220	131	129	115	117	119	121	-767	123	125	127	113	-213	240		
-105	135	-5	559	1	-35	-1	-3	-7	-349	99	-69	220	-115	135	-15	789	-9	-215	-11	-13	-17	-309	99	-79	240		
-107	137	-11	145	17	23	31	39	-155	71	101	-71	220	-117	137	-21	145	17	23	31	39	-105	71	101	-81	240		
-109	139	-13	-65	19	25	33	41	47	73	103	-73	220	-119	139	-23	-15	19	25	33	41	47	73	103	-83	240		
-111	141	-15	-19	-35	27	35	43	49	75	105	-75	220	-121	141	-25	-19	15	27	35	43	49	75	105	-85	240		
897	-867	-17	11	-187	143	37	45	51	77	-615	645	220	927	-907	-27	11	-137	143	37	45	51	77	-655	675	240		
-113	143	-19	13	21	-147	343	-183	53	79	107	-77	220	-123	143	-29	13	21	-97	293	-133	53	79	107	-87	240		
-115	145	-9	15	265	29	-379	115	55	69	109	-79	220	-125	145	-19	15	215	29	-279	115	55	69	109	-89	240		
-117	147	249	-499	59	95	61	63	67	65	111	-81	220	-127	147	359	-739	59	265	61	63	67	65	111	-91	240		
-241	-279	83	85	87	89	-503	91	93	95	97	523	220	-181	-299	83	85	87	89	-543	91	93	95	97	543	240		
309	117	-53	-55	-57	-59	533	-61	-63	-65	-259	-67	220	319	197	-63	-65	-67	-69	563	-71	-73	-75	-279	-77	240		
24a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	24b	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240		

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 60$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 180$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 230$. The magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 8} = 25 \times 100$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 75$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 260$. The magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the condition given in (3).

Result 3.13. Let's consider following magic squares of order 12 with reduced entries:

$(A59-A25)/2-A49$	A51	$(A59-A25)/2-A42$	$(A59-A25)/2-A43$	$(A59-A25)/2-A44$	$(A59-A25)/2-A45$	$3*(A25-A59)/2 + A42+A43+A44+A45 + A46+A47+A48$	$(A59-A25)/2-A46$	$(A59-A25)/2-A47$	$(A59-A25)/2-A48$	$3*A25-2*A59 + A41-A51+A49$	$(A59-A25)/2-A41$
A50	A49	A42	A43	A44	A45	$2*(A59-A25)-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48$	A46	A47	A48	A41	$2*A25-A59-A50-A49-A41$
$(A59-A25)/2-A52$	A52	A25-A13-A17	$2*A25+3*A13+A19-A14-A20$	A25-A13-A14	$A18+2*A17-7*A25+2*A13+A16+A15+2*A14+A21+A22+A24+2*A20+A23$	A25-A13-A15	A25-A13-A16	A25-A13-A18	$A25-A21-A22-A24-A20-A23-A17-A19$	A34	$(A59-A25)/2-A34$
$(A59-A25)/2-A53$	A53	A25-A13-A20	A1	$A4+A7-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A13-A7-A10$	A10	A20	A35	$(A59-A25)/2-A35$
$(A59-A25)/2-A54$	A54	A25-A13-A21	A6	A4	A5	$A7-A4-A5-A6$	$A10+A11+A12-A13+A7$	$2*A13-2*A7-A10-A11-A12$	A21	A36	$(A59-A25)/2-A36$
$(A59-A25)/2-A55$	A55	A25-A13-A22	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$A7-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$A13-A7-A11$	A11	A22	A37	$(A59-A25)/2-A37$
$3*(A25-A59)/2 + A52+A53+A54+A55+A56 + A57+A58$	$2*(A59-A25)-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58$	A25-A13-A23	$A7-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$A13-A7-A12$	A12	A23	$2*(A59-A25)-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	$3*(A25-A59)/2 + A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39 + A40$
$(A59-A25)/2-A56$	A56	A25-A13-A24	$A13-A7-A8$	$2*A13-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-A7$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+A7-2*A13$	$A13-A7-A9$	$(A13-A7)/2$	$(5*A7-3*A13)/2$	A24	A38	$(A59-A25)/2-A38$
$(A59-A25)/2-A57$	A57	A25-A13-A19	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-A13$	$3*A13-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*A7$	A9	$(5*A7-3*A13)/2$	$(A13-A7)/2$	A19	A39	$(A59-A25)/2-A39$
$(A59-A25)/2-A58$	A58	$A17+A19+7*A13+A21+A22+A24+A20+A23-6*A25$	$A14+A20-A25-A19-4*A13$	A14	$8*A25-A18-2*A17-3*A13-A16-A15-2*A14-A21-A22-A24-2*A20-A23$	A15	A16	A18	A17	A40	$(A59-A25)/2-A40$
$2*A25-A59-A41-A33-A50$	$A59-A25-A41-A49-A33$	A26	A27	A28	A29	$2*(A59-A25)-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32$	A30	A31	A32	A33	$A25-A59+2*A41 + A49+A33+A50$
$(A25-A59)/2 + A41+A49+A33$	$3*A25-2*A59 + A41+A33-A51$	$(A59-A25)/2-A26$	$(A59-A25)/2-A27$	$(A59-A25)/2-A28$	$(A59-A25)/2-A29$	$3*(A25-A59)/2 + A26+A27+A28+A29 + A30+A31+A32$	$(A59-A25)/2-A30$	$(A59-A25)/2-A31$	$(A59-A25)/2-A32$	$A59-A25-2*A41 + A51-A49-A33$	$(A59-A25)/2-A33$

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered semi-magic square** embedded with **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 8. The inner block is a **cornered magic square** of order 6 with magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. It is **semi-magic** only due to order 8 being a **semi-magic**. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (3).

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.13. First example is of **semi-magic** square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (3).

Example 3.13. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 3.13:

3a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											180	3b	mgc	S=3*T/4											200	
	-24	61	-17	-18	-19	-20	280	-21	-22	-23	79	-16	240		-39	61	-32	-33	-34	-35	325	-36	-37	-38	129	-31	200	
	60	59	52	53	54	55	-245	56	57	58	51	-70	240		60	59	52	53	54	55	-305	56	57	58	51	-50	200	
	-27	62	23	675	26	-579	25	24	22	-46	44	-9	240		-42	62	13	655	16	-509	15	14	12	-56	44	-24	200	
	-28	63	20	11	67	-11	13	20	20	30	45	-10	240		-43	63	10	11	57	-11	13	30	20	30	45	-25	200	
	-29	64	19	16	14	15	35	23	17	31	46	-11	240		-44	64	9	16	14	15	25	13	37	31	46	-26	200	
	-30	65	18	9	8	43	20	19	21	32	47	-12	240		-45	65	8	9	8	33	20	29	21	32	47	-27	200	
	350	-315	17	44	-9	33	12	18	22	33	-189	224	240		395	-375	7	34	-9	33	12	28	22	33	-249	269	200	
	-31	66	16	22	6	31	21	20	20	34	48	-13	240		-46	66	6	32	16	21	31	25	-5	34	48	-28	200	
	-32	67	21	18	34	9	19	20	20	29	49	-14	240		-47	67	11	18	34	29	19	-5	25	29	49	-29	200	
	-33	68	36	-625	24	629	25	26	28	27	50	-15	240		-48	68	96	-615	24	549	25	26	28	27	50	-30	200	
	-54	-83	36	37	38	39	-133	40	41	42	43	194	240		-34	-113	36	37	38	39	-193	40	41	42	43	224	200	
	118	63	-1	-2	-3	-4	168	-5	-6	-7	-73	-8	240		133	113	-16	-17	-18	-19	213	-20	-21	-22	-103	-23	200	
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 170$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 240$. The *magic rectangles sums* are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 20 \times 80$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 70$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 200$. It is a *magic square* as it satisfies the condition given in (3). Moreover, the *magic rectangles sums* are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 50 \times 100$ and $MR_{2 \times 8} = 50 \times 100$. It is a *magic square* as it satisfies all the four the conditions given in (4).

3.2 Double-Conditions Magic Squares

Below are results with examples of **semi-magic** squares resulting in magic squares with two conditions given in (1) and (2).

Result 3.14. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46-L	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	11*L-9*R-A36
R-L-A47	10*2*S+A35-9*L	27*L-2*A35-28*2*S-A34-A33-A32-A30-A29-A28-A26-A27-A24-A25-A21-A22-A23-A20-A31	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+18*2*S-17*L	A47
R-L-A48	A20-2*S	2*S-2*A4-2*A7-A12+A3+A6	3*A4+3*A7-A15-A2+A12-A3-A6-2*S	A2+A14-A16-4*A4-4*A7+A3+A6-A1+4*S+A15	A16+3*A4-3*S+3*A7-A3-A6+A1-A14	A3	2*S-A9-A4-A7-A5-A3	A5+A8-A16+A3+A6-A1+A9	A16+A4+A7-A3-A6+A1-A8-S	L-A20	A48
R-L-A49	A21	A2	A4+A7-A15-S	A1	2*S-A4-A7+A15-A1-A2	A5	S-A9-A4-A7	A16+2*A4-2*S+2*A7+A1-A10	A9-A4-A7+2*S-A16-A1+A10-A5	L-2*S-A21	A49
R-L-A50	A22	2*A4+2*A7-A13-S-A14+A16-A3-A6+A1-A2	4*S-3*A4-3*A7-A12+A3+A6-A13-A1	2*A4+2*A7+A12-A3-A6+A13+A15-2*S	A2+A13+A14-A16-A4-A7+A3+A6-A15	2*A4-S-A8+A16+A7-A3-A6+A1-A5	A3-A4+2*S-A16-2*A7-A1+A10	A9+A7-A3	A8+A3+A6-A10+A5-A9-A4	L-2*S-A22	A50
R-L-A51	A23	A12+A13+A14-A16-A1	A1-A4-A7+A13+2*A15+A2	2*A4+2*A7-A12-A13-A14-S+A16-2*A15-A2	2*S-A4-A7-A13	2*S-2*A4+A8-A16-A7+A6-A1	A16+3*A4-4*S+4*A7+A1+2*A9+A5-A10	3*S-A8-3*A7-A6-2*A9+A10-A5-2*A4	A4	L-2*S-A23	A51
R-L-A52	A24	A6	A9+S-A11-A6	A11-A8-A9	A8	A12	A15+S-A17-A12	A17-A14-A15	A14	L-2*S-A24	A52
R-L-A53	A25	A11	A9	A10	S-A9-A10-A11	A17	A15	A16	S-A15-A16-A17	L-2*S-A25	A53
R-L-A54	A26	A7+A8-A11	A6+A7-A10	S-A6-A7-A9	A9+A10+A11-A7-A8	A13+A14-A17	A12+A13-A16	S-A12-A13-A15	A15+A16+A17-A13-A14	L-2*S-A26	A54
A55+A54+A53+A52+A51+A50+A49+A48+A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-A37-2*A36-A38-A39-8*R+10*L	A27	S-A6-A7-A8	A10-A7-2*A9+A11	A6+A7+A8+2*A9-A10-A11	A7	S-A12-A13-A14	A16-A13-2*A15+A17	A12+A13+A14+2*A15-A16-A17	A13	L-2*S-A27	A37-A55-A53-A54-A52-A51-A50-A49-A48-A47+A45+A46-11*L+A41+A42+A43+A44+A38+A39+A40+9*R+2*A36
R-L-A55	10*L-9*2*S-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A35	27*2*S+2*A35+A34+A33+A32+A30+A29+A28+A26+A27+A24+A25+A21+A22+A23+A20-26*L+A31	L-2*S-A28	L-2*S-A29	L-2*S-A30	L-2*S-A31	L-2*S-A32	L-2*S-A33	L-2*S-A34	10*L-11*2*S-A35	A55
A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	R-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 8 composed by four equal sums magic squares of order 4. The magic square of order 10 is also a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square**. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1) and (2). The letters S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic** or **semi-magic** sums of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.14. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1) and (2).

Example 3.14. Let's consider following two **semi-magic** and magic square based on the Result 3.14:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											50	mgc	L=5*R/6 and T=4*L/5											210		
381	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-136	230	386	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-11	210		
-7	-175	295	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-227	57	230	-22	-130	160	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-142	57	210		
-8	-110	85	-91	209	-133	13	62	44	-49	150	58	230	-23	-110	85	-91	209	-133	13	62	44	-49	145	58	210		
-9	31	12	-64	11	111	15	20	-61	96	9	59	230	-24	31	12	-64	11	111	15	20	-61	96	4	59	210		
-10	32	-59	160	-37	6	-50	88	23	9	8	60	230	-25	32	-59	160	-37	6	-50	88	23	9	3	60	210		
-11	33	32	65	-113	86	92	-100	64	14	7	61	230	-26	33	32	65	-113	86	92	-100	64	14	2	61	210		
-12	34	16	52	-16	18	22	46	-22	24	6	62	230	-27	34	16	52	-16	18	22	46	-22	24	1	62	210		
-13	35	21	19	20	10	27	25	26	-8	5	63	230	-28	35	21	19	20	10	27	25	26	-8	0	63	210		
-14	36	14	13	18	25	20	19	0	31	4	64	230	-29	36	14	13	18	25	20	19	0	31	-1	64	210		
-98	37	19	-14	48	17	1	-20	66	23	3	148	230	12	37	19	-14	48	17	1	-20	66	23	-2	23	210		
-15	227	-255	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	215	65	230	-30	177	-125	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	165	65	210		
46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	-331	230	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	-351	210		
15a	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	15b	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{4 \times 4} = 70$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 140$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 180$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 230$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{4 \times 4} = 70$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 140$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 175$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 210$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Result 3.15. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+A_{34}+A_{35}+A_{36}+A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{39}-L$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	$11*L-9*R-A_{29}$
R-L-A40	$10*4*m-9*L$	$27*L-28*4*m-A_{27}-A_{26}-A_{25}-A_{23}-A_{22}-A_{21}-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{17}-A_{18}-A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_{24}$	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	A26	A27	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{13}+72*m-17*L$	A40
R-L-A41	$A_{13}-4*m$	$A_1-A_3-A_5-A_6-A_8+A_7$	$A_6+A_8-2*m+A_{11}+A_1-A_3-A_5$	$2*m$	$2*m+2*A_3+2*A_5-A_7-A_{11}-2*A_1$	$A_5+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}+A_{10}-A_9$	$2*m-A_9-A_5-A_{10}$	$A_9-2*A_3+A_7+A_{11}$	A9	L-A13	A41
R-L-A42	A14	$m+A_3+A_5+A_6+A_8-A_7-A_1$	$3*m+A_3+A_5-A_6-A_8-A_{11}-A_1$	$(-m)$	$A_7-m+A_{11}+2*A_1-2*A_3-2*A_5$	$m+A_9-A_{10}+A_{11}-A_5-2*A_3+A_7$	$A_9+A_5+A_{10}-m$	$m-A_9+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	$m-A_9$	$L-4*m-A_{14}$	A42
R-L-A43	A15	$2*A_3+2*A_5-A_7-A_{11}-A_1$	A1	$A_6+A_8+A_{11}-A_3-A_5$	$2*m+A_7-A_3-A_5-A_6-A_8$	$A_5+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	A5	$2*m+A_7+A_{11}-A_{10}-2*A_3-2*A_5$	A10	$L-4*m-A_{15}$	A43
R-L-A44	A16	$A_1+m-2*A_3-2*A_5+A_7+A_{11}$	$m-A_1$	$m+A_3+A_5-A_6-A_8-A_{11}$	$A_3+A_5+A_6+A_8-A_7-m$	$m+A_7+A_{11}-A_5-2*A_3$	$m-A_5$	$2*A_3+2*A_5-A_7-A_{11}+A_{10}-m$	$m-A_{10}$	$L-4*m-A_{16}$	A44
R-L-A45	A17	$A_3+A_2-A_7-A_{11}+A_4$	$2*m-A_3-A_2-A_4$	$A_7+A_{11}-A_3$	A3	$2*m-A_6-A_8-A_{11}$	$A_6+A_8-A_7$	A7	A11	$L-4*m-A_{17}$	A45
R-L-A46	A18	$m+A_7+A_{11}-A_4-A_3-A_2$	$A_3+A_2+A_4-m$	$m+A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	$m-A_3$	$A_6+A_8+A_{11}-m$	$m+A_7-A_6-A_8$	$m-A_7$	$m-A_{11}$	$L-4*m-A_{18}$	A46
R-L-A47	A19	$A_2+2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}$	A2	$2*m+A_7+A_{11}-2*A_2-A_4-2*A_3$	A4	$A_6+A_{11}-A_7$	A6	A8	$2*m+A_7-2*A_6-A_8-A_{11}$	$L-4*m-A_{19}$	A47
$10*L-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-2*A_{29}-A_{30}-8*R+A_{48}-A_{35}-A_{34}+A_{47}+A_{46}+A_{45}+A_{44}+A_{43}+A_{42}+A_{41}+A_{40}-A_{39}-A_{38}-A_{37}-A_{36}$	A20	$m+A_7+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3$	$m-A_2$	$2*A_3-A_7-A_{11}+2*A_2+A_4-m$	$m-A_4$	$m+A_7-A_{11}-A_6$	$m-A_6$	$m-A_8$	$2*A_6+A_8+A_{11}-A_7-m$	$L-4*m-A_{20}$	$A_{30}+A_{36}-11*L+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+2*A_{29}+9*R-A_{48}+A_{35}+A_{34}-A_{47}-A_{46}-A_{45}-A_{44}-A_{43}-A_{42}-A_{41}-A_{40}+A_{39}+A_{38}+A_{37}$
R-L-A48	$10*L-9*4*m-A_{13}-A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{20}$	$27*4*m+A_{27}+A_26+A_{25}+A_{23}+A_{22}+A_{21}+A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{13}-26*L+A_{24}$	$L-4*m-A_{21}$	$L-4*m-A_{22}$	$L-4*m-A_{23}$	$L-4*m-A_{24}$	$L-4*m-A_{25}$	$L-4*m-A_{26}$	$L-4*m-A_{27}$	$10*L-11*4*m$	A48
A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	$R-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-A_{34}-A_{35}-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of orders 10 and 12 embedded with a *striped pandiagonal magic square* of order 8. It is composed by 8 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In order to bring it as a magic square we need the condition given in (1). The letters T, L and R represents respectively the *magic* or *semi-magic* sums of orders 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.15. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 3.15. Let's consider following two *semi-magic* and magic square based on the Result 3.15:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												-540	mgc	L=5*R/6 and T=4*L/5												180
324	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	-259	220	334	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-9	180		
10	-640	1630	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	-1068	50	220	-20	-150	240	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	-178	50	180		
9	-57	-34	-2	40	36	4	-14	31	19	137	51	220	-21	-97	-34	-22	60	56	4	6	31	19	127	51	180		
8	24	54	22	-20	-16	16	34	-11	1	56	52	220	-22	24	64	52	-30	-26	26	24	-1	11	6	52	180		
7	25	7	11	27	-5	3	15	2	20	55	53	220	-23	25	7	11	27	15	3	15	22	20	5	53	180		
6	26	13	9	-7	25	17	5	18	0	54	54	220	-24	26	23	19	3	15	27	15	8	10	4	54	180		
5	27	1	1	25	13	-15	17	17	21	53	55	220	-25	27	1	21	25	13	5	17	17	21	3	55	180		
4	28	19	19	-5	7	35	3	3	-1	52	56	220	-26	28	29	9	5	17	25	13	13	9	2	56	180		
3	29	0	12	14	14	20	16	18	-14	51	57	220	-27	29	0	12	34	14	20	16	18	6	1	57	180		
-197	30	20	8	6	6	0	4	2	34	50	257	220	23	30	30	18	-4	16	10	14	12	24	0	7	180		
2	668	-1550	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	720	58	220	-28	208	-210	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	180	58	180		
39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	-264	220	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	-304	180		
22a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	22b	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $S_{8 \times 8} = 80$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 160$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 220$. Moreover, the *magic rectangles sums* are 20×40 .
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $S_{8 \times 8} = 120$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 150$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 180$. It is a *magic square* because it satisfied the conditions given in (1) and (2). Moreover, the *magic rectangles sums* are 30×60 .

Result 3.16. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$A_{51}+A_{52}+A_{53}+A_{54}+A_{55}+A_{56}+A_{57}+A_{58}+A_{59}+A_{60}+A_{61}-L$	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	R-L-A59	R-L-A60	R-L-A61	$11*L-9*R-A_{51}$
R-L-A62	$10*T-9*L$	$27*L-28*T-A_{49}-A_{48}-A_{47}-A_{45}-A_{44}-A_{43}-A_{41}-A_{42}-A_{39}-A_{40}-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{35}-A_{46}$	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	$A_{41}+A_{42}+A_{39}+A_{40}+A_{36}+A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{35}+18*T-17*L$	A62
R-L-A63	A35-T	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}-A_{15}$	A4	A7	A11	A15	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}$	T-S-A29	A29	L-A35	A63
R-L-A64	A36	$S-A_{12}-A_5-A_8-A_{16}-A_{19}$	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	T-S-A30	A30	L-T-A36	A64
R-L-A65	A37	$A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_1-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_8+A_{12}+A_{16}$	$S-A_4-A_5-A_{12}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_{17}-A_7-A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_9-A_{11}+A_1+A_2+A_3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	T-S-A31	A31	L-T-A37	A65
R-L-A66	A38	A1	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_1-A_{18}-A_{14}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}$	$A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_6+A_{19}-A_3$	A14	A18	A21	T-S-A32	A32	L-T-A38	A66
R-L-A67	A39	A2	A6	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}-A_9+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{10}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}-A_7-A_8$	$A_5+A_{14}+A_{10}+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+2*A_{20}-A_4+A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}+2*A_9-2*A_6+2*A_{19}-A_{11}-A_2-A_3-S$	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{23}+A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_5-A_9-A_{14}$	A22	T-S-A33	A33	L-T-A39	A67
R-L-A68	A40	A3	$A_{12}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_7+A_8+A_{15}+A_9-2*A_6+A_{19}+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3-S$	A10	$2*S+A_4-A_8+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_9+2*A_6-2*A_{19}+A_2+A_3-A_{12}-A_5-2*A_{14}-A_{10}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-2*A_{20}$	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}+A_5+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	A23	$2*S-2*T+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}$	$3*T-3*S-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}$	L-T-A40	A68
R-L-A69	A41	T-S-A25	$A_{30}-A_{29}-2*A_9+A_{13}-A_{25}+2*S-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A28	$2*A_{25}+A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}-A_{30}+A_{29}+2*A_9-A_{13}-T-S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4-A_{11}+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	(T-S)/2	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	L-T-A41	A69
$10*L+A_{63}+A_{69}+A_{70}-8*R+A_{67}+A_{68}+A_{64}+A_{65}+A_{66}+A_{62}-A_{61}-A_{60}-A_{59}-A_{58}-A_{57}-A_{56}-A_{52}-A_{55}-A_{53}-A_{54}-2*A_{51}$	A42	A25	$A_{29}-A_{30}+2*A_9-A_{13}+T+A_{25}-A_{11}-3*S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	A26	A27	A28	$A_{30}-A_{29}-A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-2*A_9+A_{13}+2*T-2*A_{25}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A42	$A_{52}+A_{55}+A_{53}+A_{54}+2*A_{51}-11*L-A_{63}-A_{69}-A_{70}+9*R-A_{67}-A_{68}-A_{64}-A_{65}-A_{66}-A_{62}+A_{61}+A_{60}+A_{59}+A_{58}+A_{57}+A_{56}$
R-L-A70	$10*L-9*T-A_{35}-A_{36}-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}-A_{41}-A_{42}$	$27*T+A_{49}+A_{48}+A_{47}+A_{45}+A_{44}+A_{43}+A_{41}+A_{42}+A_{39}+A_{40}+A_{36}+A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{35}-26*L+A_{46}$	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	L-T-A46	L-T-A47	L-T-A48	L-T-A49	$10*L-11*T$	A70
A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A60	A61	$R-A_{51}-A_{52}-A_{53}-A_{54}-A_{55}-A_{56}-A_{57}-A_{58}-A_{59}-A_{60}-A_{61}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of orders 10 and 12 embedded with a **cornered magic square** of order 8 with a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 6 at upper-left corner. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1) and (2). The letters S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.16. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1) and (2).

Example 3.16. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.16:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											200	mgc	L=5*R/6 and T=4*L/5											270		
516	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-91	260	501	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-16	270		
-22	-190	130	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	-122	72	260	-27	-225	255	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	-197	72	270		
-23	-125	78	14	17	21	25	-55	31	39	165	73	260	-28	-135	78	14	17	21	25	-55	41	39	180	73	270		
-24	46	-10	15	18	22	26	29	30	40	-6	74	260	-29	46	-10	15	18	22	26	29	40	40	-1	74	270		
-25	47	-4	5	19	23	27	30	29	41	-7	75	260	-30	47	-4	5	19	23	27	30	39	41	-2	75	270		
-26	48	11	-71	77	24	28	31	28	42	-8	76	260	-31	48	11	-71	77	24	28	31	38	42	-3	76	270		
-27	49	12	16	-51	160	-69	32	27	43	-9	77	260	-32	49	12	16	-51	160	-69	32	37	43	-4	77	270		
-28	50	13	121	20	-150	63	33	65	5	-10	78	260	-33	50	13	121	20	-150	63	33	45	35	-5	78	270		
-29	51	35	-172	34	33	32	248	35	-75	-11	79	260	-34	51	45	-172	44	43	42	238	40	-100	-6	79	270		
-83	52	35	242	36	37	38	-178	-75	35	-12	133	260	-13	52	35	252	36	37	38	-158	-100	40	-7	58	270		
-30	182	-90	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	230	80	260	-35	242	-210	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	270	80	270		
61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	-466	260	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	-456	270		
17a	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	17b	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 180$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 210$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 260$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 60 \times 180$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 225$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 270$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 80 \times 240$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Result 3.17. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A_{37}+A_{38}+A_{39}+A_{40}+A_{41}+A_{42}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{45}+A_{46}+A_{47}-L$	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	$11*L-9*R-A_{37}$
R-L-A48	$10*T-9*L$	$27*L-28*T-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{24}-A_{25}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}-A_{34}-A_{35}$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	$A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{24}+A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}+A_{28}+18*T-17*L$	A48
R-L-A49	A21-T	$2*M/3-A_6$	$A_6+A_7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A_7$	$2*M/3-A_2$	$A_2+A_3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A_3$	T-2*M-A15	A15	L-A21	A49
R-L-A50	A22	$A_6+A_8-M/3$	$M+A_1-A_6-A_7-A_8$	$M/3+A_7-A_1$	$A_2+A_4-M/3$	$5*M/3-A_3-A_2-A_4-A_5$	$A_3+A_5-M/3$	T-2*M-A16	A16	L-T-A22	A50
R-L-A51	A23	$2*M/3-A_8$	$M/3+A_8-A_1$	A1	$2*M/3-A_4$	$A_4+A_5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A_5$	T-2*M-A17	A17	L-T-A23	A51
R-L-A52	A24	A2	M-A2-A3	A3	A6	M-A6-A7	A7	T-2*M-A18	A18	L-T-A24	A52
R-L-A53	A25	M-A2-A4	$A_2+A_3+A_4+A_5-M$	M-A3-A5	M-A6-A8	$A_6+A_7+A_8-A_1-M/3$	$M/3-A_7+A_1$	T-2*M-A19	A19	L-T-A25	A53
R-L-A54	A26	A4	M-A4-A5	A5	A8	$M/3-A_8+A_1$	$2*M/3-A_1$	$4*M-2*T+A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}+A_{18}+A_{19}$	$3*T-6*M-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}-A_{19}$	L-T-A26	A54
R-L-A55	A27	$2*T-10*M/3-A_{10}+A_{15}-A_{16}-2*A_6-A_7-A_8$	T-2*M-A10	T-2*M-A11	T-2*M-A12	T-2*M-A13	$16*M/3-3*T+2*A_{10}-A_{15}+A_{16}+2*A_6+A_7+A_8+A_{11}+A_{12}+A_{13}$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$(14*M-5*T)/2$	L-T-A27	A55
$A_{56}+A_{54}+A_{55}-L+A_{52}+A_{53}+A_{49}+A_{50}+A_{51}+A_{48}+11*L-8*R-A_{47}-A_{46}-A_{45}-A_{44}-A_{43}-A_{42}-A_{41}-A_{40}-A_{39}-A_{38}-2*A_{37}$	A28	$A_{10}-A_{15}-T+4*M/3+A_{16}+2*A_6+A_7+A_8$	A10	A11	A12	A13	$4*T-22*M/3-2*A_{10}+A_{15}-A_{16}-2*A_6-A_7-A_8-A_{11}-A_{12}-A_{13}$	$(14*M-5*T)/2$	$(T-2*M)/2$	L-T-A28	$A_{38}-A_{56}-A_{54}-A_{55}-A_{52}-A_{53}-A_{49}-A_{50}-A_{51}-A_{48}-11*L+9*R+A_{47}+A_{46}+A_{45}+A_{44}+A_{43}+A_{42}+A_{41}+A_{40}+A_{39}+2*A_{37}$
R-L-A56	$10*L-9*T-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{24}-A_{25}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}$	$A_{21}+27*T+A_{35}+A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_2+4*A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}-26*L+A_{34}$	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	$10*L-11*T$	A56
A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	$R-A_{37}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}-A_{41}-A_{42}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{45}-A_{46}-A_{47}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of orders 10 and 12 embedded with a **cornered magic square** of order 8 with a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 6 at upper-left corner. This magic square of order 6 is composed of four equal sums **semi-magic squares** of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1) and (2). The letters M, S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.17. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1) and (2).

Example 3.17. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.17:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											330	mgc	L=5*R/6 and T=4*L/5											270		
372	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	83	230	347	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-2	270		
-28	-200	350	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-244	58	230	-13	-225	465	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-309	58	270		
-29	-129	14	18	13	18	10	17	45	25	169	59	230	-14	-149	24	13	23	28	5	27	35	25	194	59	270		
-30	32	19	5	21	11	21	13	44	26	8	60	230	-15	32	14	20	26	6	46	8	34	26	13	60	270		
-31	33	12	22	11	16	14	15	43	27	7	61	230	-16	33	22	27	11	26	9	25	33	27	12	61	270		
-32	34	12	20	13	16	12	17	42	28	6	62	230	-17	34	12	35	13	16	27	17	32	28	11	62	270		
-33	35	19	9	17	11	25	9	41	29	5	63	230	-18	35	34	-6	32	26	20	14	31	29	10	63	270		
-34	36	14	16	15	18	8	19	-5	75	4	64	230	-19	36	14	31	15	18	13	29	15	45	9	64	270		
-35	37	82	50	49	48	47	-66	35	-85	3	65	230	-20	37	72	40	39	38	37	-46	30	-30	8	65	270		
99	38	-12	20	21	22	23	136	-85	35	2	-69	230	29	38	-12	20	21	22	23	106	-30	30	7	16	270		
-36	284	-310	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	240	66	230	-21	354	-420	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	270	66	270		
47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	-342	230	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	-302	270		
19a	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	19b	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 45$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 90$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 200$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 230$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 70 \times 210$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 60$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 180$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 225$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 270$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 60 \times 180$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Result 3.18. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48-L$	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	$11*L-9*R-A38$
R-L-A49	$10*T-9*L$	$27*L-28*T-A36-A35-A34-A32-A31-A30-A28-A29-A26-A27-A23-A24-A25-A22-A33$	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	$18*T-17*L+A28+A29+A26+A27+A23+A24+A25+A22$	A49
R-L-A50	A22-T	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-A22	A50
R-L-A51	A23	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	$T-4*S-A17+A1+2*M+2*A9+2*A8+3*A4$	$A17-A1-2*M+3*S-2*A9-2*A8-3*A4$	L-T-A23	A51
R-L-A52	A24	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	M-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	$2*A17+A19+A20-A1-2*M+5*S-2*T-2*A9-2*A8-3*A4+A18$	$3*T-6*S-A19-A20-2*A17+A1+2*M+2*A9+2*A8+3*A4-A18$	L-T-A24	A52
R-L-A53	A25	M-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A25	A53
R-L-A54	A26	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	T-S-A19	A19	L-T-A26	A54
R-L-A55	A27	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	T-S-A20	A20	L-T-A27	A55
R-L-A56	A28	$T+2*S-3*M-2*A9-2*A8$	$2*A10+2*A12-M+2*S-2*A9-2*A8$	$A16-4*S+4*M-T+4*A9+4*A8+A15+A14-2*A12-2*A10$	T-S-A14	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A28	A56
$10*L-8*R+A57+A56+A55+A54+A53+A52+A51+A50+A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-A39-2*A38$	a43	$2*A9+2*A8-3*S+3*M$	$2*A9+2*A8+M+T-3*S-2*A10-2*A12$	$2*T+3*S-A15-A14-4*M-4*A9-4*A8+2*A12+2*A10-A16$	A14	A15	A16	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A29	$9*R-A57-A55-A56-A53-A54-A50-A51-A52+A48+A42+A39+A46+A47+A41+A43+A44+A45+A40-11*L-A49+2*A38$
R-L-A57	$10*L-9*T-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29$	$27*T+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A28+A29+A26+A27+A23+A24+A25+A22-26*L$	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	$10*L-11*T$	A57
A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	0	A48	R-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered semi-magic square embedded with cornered magic squares of orders 6 and 8. These are semi-magic only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.18. First example is of semi-magic squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Example 3.18. *Let's consider a following semi-magic square based on the Result 3.18:*

5a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											130	5b	mgc	L=5*R/6 and T=4*L/5											300
	333	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	-268	330		333	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	2	300
	21	-150	285	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	-186	59	330		-9	-250	565	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	-366	59	300
	20	-178	11	77	-11	13	40	20	33	27	218	60	330		-10	-168	11	67	-11	13	20	20	53	27	218	60	300
	19	33	16	14	15	45	3	57	-110	170	7	61	330		-11	33	16	14	15	35	23	17	-20	100	17	61	300
	18	34	9	8	53	20	39	21	164	-104	6	62	330		-12	34	9	8	43	20	19	21	54	26	16	62	300
	17	35	54	-9	33	12	38	22	32	28	5	63	330		-13	35	44	-9	33	12	18	22	52	28	15	63	300
	16	36	42	56	-19	41	30	0	31	29	4	64	330		-14	36	22	6	31	21	20	20	51	29	14	64	300
	15	37	18	4	79	19	0	30	30	30	3	65	330		-15	37	18	34	9	19	20	20	50	30	13	65	300
	14	38	166	220	-311	36	35	34	30	0	2	66	330		-16	38	126	170	-221	56	55	54	40	-80	12	66	300
	-204	39	-106	-160	371	24	25	26	0	30	1	284	330		36	39	-46	-90	301	24	25	26	-80	40	11	14	300
	13	326	-245	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	190	67	330		-17	416	-515	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	300	67	300
	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	-253	330		48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	-283	300
	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330		300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 90$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 210$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 250$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 330$. In this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 60 \times 120$ and $MR_{2 \times 6} = 60 \times 180$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 200$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 250$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 300$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (??). Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$ and $MR_{2 \times 6} = 80 \times 240$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Result 3.19. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49-L	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	11*L-9*R-A39
R-L-A50	10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A37-A36-A35-A33-A32-A31-A29-A30-A27-A28-A24-A25-A26-A23-A34	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	18*T-17*L+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23	A50
59-L-A51	A23-T	4*S-6*M+A11	S+2*A12+2*A13-4*A11-M	2*A11+9*M-6*S-A12-A13	S-A12-M	S-A13-M	A11	T-S-A15	A15	L-A23	A51
R-L-A52	A24	4*M-3*S+A8+A9+A10	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	4*S-A8-A9-A10-5*M	T-8*S-A15-A1-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-3*A4+10*M	A15+A1+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+7*S+3*A4-10*M	L-T-A24	A52
R-L-A53	A25	S-A8-M	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A8	2*A15+A17+A18+A1-2*T+9*S+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+3*A4-10*M+A16	3*T-10*S-A17-A18-2*A15-A1-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-3*A4+10*M-A16	L-T-A25	A53
R-L-A54	A26	S-A9-M	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A9	T-S-A16	A16	L-T-A26	A54
R-L-A55	A27	S-A10-M	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-T-A27	A55
R-L-A56	A28	5*M-A11-3*S	4*A11-2*A12-2*A13	7*S+A12+A13-2*A11-10*M	A12	A13	5*M-A11-3*S	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A28	A56
R-L-A57	A29	T-S+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+2*A1+7*S+6*A4-11*M	8*S+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+2*A1+6*A4-11*M	A20+A19+A21-T-2*A12-2*A8-2*A13+4*A11-4*A1-14*S-12*A4+22*M	T-S-A19	T-S-A20	T-S-A21	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A29	A57
10*L-8*R+A58+A56+A57+A54+A55+A51+A52+A53-A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40+A50-2*A39	A30	11*M-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-2*A1-7*S-6*A4	T-9*S-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-2*A1-6*A4+11*M	2*T+13*S+2*A12+2*A8+2*A13-4*A11+4*A1+12*A4-22*M-A20-A19-A21	A19	A20	A21	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A30	9*R-A58-A57-A56-A55-A54-A53-A52-A51-A50+A49+A43+A40+A47+A48+A42+A44+A45+A46+A41-11*L+2*A39
R-L-A58	10*L-9*T-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30	27*T+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23-26*L	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	10*L-11*T	A58
A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	R-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **cornered magic squares** of order 8 with **single-digit bordered magic square** of order 6 at the left upper corner having magic square of order 4. These are **semi-magic** only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need some conditions. The conditions are the same as given in (1) and (2).

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.19. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Example 3.19. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 3.19:

6a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											290	6b	mgc	L=5*R/6 and T=4*L/5											360
	384	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	11	250		294	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	11	360
	-20	-190	310	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	-218	60	250		0	-300	780	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	-488	60	360
	-21	-137	-19	36	57	8	7	21	35	25	177	61	250		-1	-207	101	86	-123	58	57	21	15	25	267	61	360
	-22	34	47	11	67	-11	13	-17	-9	69	6	62	250		-2	34	-63	11	107	-11	13	143	-259	299	26	62	360
	-23	35	12	16	14	15	35	18	55	5	5	63	250		-3	35	62	16	14	15	75	18	325	-285	25	63	360
	-24	36	11	9	8	43	20	19	34	26	4	64	250		-4	36	61	9	8	83	20	19	14	26	24	64	360
	-25	37	10	44	-9	33	12	20	33	27	3	65	250		-5	37	60	84	-9	33	12	20	13	27	23	65	360
	-26	38	49	-6	-27	22	23	49	32	28	2	66	250		-6	38	-21	-6	203	22	23	-21	12	28	22	66	360
	-27	39	77	127	-114	31	30	29	30	-40	1	67	250		-7	39	247	407	-564	11	10	9	20	100	21	67	360
	33	40	-17	-67	174	29	30	31	-40	30	0	7	250		53	40	-207	-367	604	29	30	31	100	20	20	7	360
	-28	278	-270	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	230	68	250		-8	548	-720	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	360	68	360
	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	-344	250		49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	-234	360
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250		360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums of the first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 170$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 210$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 250$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 60 \times 180$.
- (ii) The *magic sums of the second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 120$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 200$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 240$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 300$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 360$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 120$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1) and (2).

Result 3.20. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55-L	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	11*L-9*R-A45
R-L-A56	$2*(L-S)/2-A42-A28-A35$	$2*A35+A42+A41+A28-A29-2*A22+(5*S-3*L)/2-A21$	A23	A24	A25	A26	$3*(L-S)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27$	A27	$A29+2*A22-A28+A21-A35-A41$	A28	A56
R-L-A57	A21	A22	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(L-S)/2-A25$	$(L-S)/2-A26$	$A23+A24+A25+A26+A27-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A27$	$(3*S-L)/2-A21-A22-A29$	A29	A57
R-L-A58	$3*(L-S)/2-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20$	$A16+A17+A18+A19+A20-2*(L-S)/2$	$4*S-6*M+A12$	$S-M+2*A14+2*A13-4*A12$	$2*A12+9*M-6*S-A14-A13$	S-M-A14	S-M-A13	A12	$(L-S)/2-A36$	A36	A58
R-L-A59	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	$4*M-3*S+A9+A10+A11$	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	$4*S-5*M-A9-A10-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A37$	A37	A59
R-L-A60	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$	S-M-A9	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A9	$S-L+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	$3*(L-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A60
R-L-A61	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$	S-M-A10	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A10	$(L-S)/2-A38$	A38	A61
R-L-A62	A19	$(L-S)/2-A19$	S--M-A11	M-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A11	$(L-S)/2-A39$	A39	A62
R-L-A63	A20	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$5*M-3*S-A12$	$4*A12-2*A14-2*A13$	$7*(L-2*(L-S)/2)+A14+A13-2*A12-10*M$	A14	A13	$5*M-A12-3*S$	$(L-S)/2-A40$	A40	A63
$10*L-8*R+A64+A63+A62+A61+A60+A59+A58+A57+A56-A55-A54-A53-A52-A51-A50-A49-A48-A47-A46-2*A45$	$(5*S-3*L)/2+A42+A28-A21$	$(3*L-5*S)/2-A28+A21+A22-A35+A29$	$(L-S)/2-A30$	$A30+A31+A32+A33+A34-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A31$	$(L-S)/2-A32$	$(L-S)/2-A33$	$(L-S)/2-A34$	A35+A28-A22	$(3*S-L)/2-A28-A29-A42$	$9*R-A64-A62-A63-A60-A61-A57-A58-A59+A55+A49+A46+A53+A54+A48+A50+A51+A52+A47-11*L-A56+2*A45$
R-L-A64	A35	$(3*S-L)/2-A35-A42-A41$	A30	$3*(L-S)/2-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A41	A42	A64
A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	R-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 12 embedded with **double-digit magic square** of order 10. The inner part is again a **single-digit bordered magic square** of order 6 with magic square of order 4. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1) and (4). The letters M, S, L and R represents respectively the **magic** or **semi-magic** sums of orders 4, 6, 10 and 12.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.20. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (??).

Example 3.20. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 3.20:

9a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											120	9b	mgc	L=5*R/6											240
	510	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-205	200		450	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-35	95	240
	-16	-75	97	33	34	35	36	-85	37	0	38	66	200		-36	-75	157	33	34	35	36	-85	37	0	38	66	240
	-17	31	32	-3	-4	-5	-6	115	-7	-42	39	67	200		-37	31	32	-3	-4	-5	-6	115	-7	18	39	67	240
	-18	-50	80	-98	16	177	-14	-13	22	-16	46	68	200		-38	-50	80	142	76	-183	46	47	22	-16	46	68	240
	-19	26	4	110	11	67	-11	13	-100	-17	47	69	200		-39	26	4	-70	11	67	-11	13	140	-17	47	69	240
	-20	27	3	-9	16	14	15	35	19	180	-150	70	200		-40	27	3	51	16	14	15	35	19	180	-150	70	240
	-21	28	2	-10	9	8	43	20	20	-18	48	71	200		-41	28	2	50	9	8	43	20	20	-18	48	71	240
	-22	29	1	-11	44	-9	33	12	21	-19	49	72	200		-42	29	1	49	44	-9	33	12	21	-19	49	72	240
	-23	30	0	108	-6	-167	24	23	108	-20	50	73	200		-43	30	0	-72	-6	253	24	23	-72	-20	50	73	240
	-185	59	19	-10	150	-11	-12	-13	-14	51	-69	235	200		95	119	-41	-10	150	-11	-12	-13	-14	51	-9	-65	240
	-24	45	-88	40	-120	41	42	43	44	51	52	74	200		-44	45	-28	40	-120	41	42	43	44	51	52	74	240
	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	-460	200		55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	-420	240
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} = 90$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 150$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 200$. Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 150$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 210$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. We get it a magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (4). Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$.

Result 3.21. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

(R-T)/2-A52	A54	(R-T)/2-A45	(R-T)/2-A46	(R-T)/2-A47	(R-T)/2-A48	$3*(T-R)/2 + A45+A46+A47 + A48+A49+A50 + A51$	(R-T)/2-A49	(R-T)/2-A50	(R-T)/2-A51	$3*T-2*R+A44-A54+A52$	(R-T)/2-A44
A53	A52	A45	A46	A47	A48	$2*(R-T)-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51$	A49	A50	A51	A44	$2*T-R-A53-A52-A44$
(R-T)/2-A55	A55	T-S-A20	$2*T+3*S+A22-A17-A23$	T-S-A17	$A21+2*A20-7*T+2*S+A19+A18+2*A17+A24+A25+A27+2*A23+A26$	T-S-A18	T-S-A19	T-S-A21	$T-A24-A25-A27-A23-A26-A20-A22$	A37	(R-T)/2-A37
(R-T)/2-A56	A56	T-S-A23	S-M-A15	S-A13-M	$2*A11-3*A4-A13-A8+A9+M$	$3*A4-3*S+2*A13+A14+2*A8+A9-A10+2*A15+2*M$	S-A14-M	$S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A15$	a38	A38	(R-T)/2-A38
(R-T)/2-A57	A57	T-S-A24	S-M-A9	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	A9	a39	A39	(R-T)/2-A39
(R-T)/2-A58	A58	T-S-A25	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	a40	A40	(R-T)/2-A40
$3*(T-R)/2+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61$	$2*(R-T)-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61$	T-S-A26	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A11	a41	$2*(R-T)-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	$3*(T-R)/2+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43$
(R-T)/2-A59	A59	T-S-A27	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A8	a42	A41	(R-T)/2-A41
(R-T)/2-A60	A60	T-S-A22	$A8-4*S+A9+A10+A11+A15+5*M$	A13	$S-2*A11+3*A4+A13+A8-A9-2*M$	$4*S+A11-3*A4-2*A13-A14-2*A8-A10-2*A15-3*M$	A14	A15	a37	A42	(R-T)/2-A42
(R-T)/2-A61	A61	$A20+A22+7*S+A24+A25+A27+A23+A26-6*T$	$A17+A23-T-A22-4*S$	A17	$8*T-A21-2*A20-3*S-A19-A18-2*A17-A24-A25-A27-2*A23-A26$	A18	A19	A21	a35	A43	(R-T)/2-A43
$2*T-R-A44-A36-A53$	R-T-A44-A52-A36	A29	A30	A31	A32	$2*(R-T)-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35$	A33	A34	a50	A36	$T-R+2*A44+A52+A36+A53$
$(T-R)/2+A44+A52+A36$	$3*T-2*R+A44+A36-A54$	(R-T)/2-A29	(R-T)/2-A30	(R-T)/2-A31	(R-T)/2-A32	$3*(T-R)/2+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35$	(R-T)/2-A33	(R-T)/2-A34	(R-T)/2-A35	$R-T-2*A44+A54-A52-A36$	(R-T)/2-A36

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered semi-magic** square embedded with **single-digit bordered semi-magic** squares of orders 6 and 8. The inner block is a magic square of order 4. It becomes **semi-magic** only due to orders 6 and 8 being a **semi-magic**. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a conditions given in (3) and (4).

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.21. First example is of **semi-magic** square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (3) and (4).

Example 3.21. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 3.21:

4a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											260	4b	mgc	S=3*T/4 and M=2*S/3											200
	-88	117	-74	-76	-78	-80	660	-82	-84	-86	143	-72	200		-93	117	-79	-81	-83	-85	675	-87	-89	-91	173	-77	200
	115	113	99	101	103	105	-635	107	109	111	97	-225	200		115	113	99	101	103	105	-655	107	109	111	97	-205	200
	-94	119	-19	615	-13	-133	-15	-17	-21	-247	83	-58	200		-99	119	-9	635	-3	-203	-5	-7	-11	-237	83	-63	200
	-96	121	-25	1	5	58	84	3	-31	55	85	-60	200		-101	121	-15	1	5	58	84	3	-31	55	85	-65	200
	-98	123	-27	13	11	65	-11	15	27	57	87	-62	200		-103	123	-17	13	11	65	-11	15	27	57	87	-67	200
	-100	125	-29	11	21	17	19	23	29	59	89	-64	200		-105	125	-19	11	21	17	19	23	29	59	89	-69	200
	800	-775	-31	9	7	5	39	29	31	61	-523	548	200		815	-795	-21	9	7	5	39	29	31	61	-543	563	200
	-102	127	-33	15	41	-7	33	13	25	63	91	-66	200		-107	127	-23	15	41	-7	33	13	25	63	91	-71	200
	-104	129	-23	71	35	-18	-44	37	39	53	93	-68	200		-109	129	-13	71	35	-18	-44	37	39	53	93	-73	200
	-106	131	337	-585	43	163	45	47	51	49	95	-70	200		-111	131	277	-595	43	243	45	47	51	49	95	-75	200
	-193	-241	67	69	71	73	-411	75	77	79	81	453	200		-173	-251	67	69	71	73	-431	75	77	79	81	463	200
	266	111	-42	-44	-46	-48	436	-50	-52	-54	-221	-56	200		271	141	-47	-49	-51	-53	451	-55	-57	-59	-231	-61	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the *first example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} = 120$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 150$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 240$. In this case there four magic rectangles with magic sums $MR_{2 \times 8} = 25 \times 100$.
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the *second example* are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 200$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (??). Moreover, in this case there are four magic rectangles with magic sums $MR_{2 \times 8} = 20 \times 80$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (3) and (4).

3.3 Three-Conditions Magic Squares

Below are results with examples of **semi-magic** squares resulting in magic squares with two conditions given in (1), (2) and (3).

Result 3.22. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62+A63-L$	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	R-L-A59	R-L-A60	R-L-A61	R-L-A62	R-L-A63	$11*L-9*R-A53$
R-L-A64	$10*T-9*L$	$27*L-28*T-A51-A50-A49-A47-A46-A45-A43-A44-A41-A42-A38-A39-A40-A37-A48$	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	$A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A37+18*T-17*L$	A64
R-L-A65	A37-T	T-S-A28	$2*T+3*S+A30-A25-A31$	T-S-A25	$A29+2*A28-7*T+2*S+A27+A26+2*A25+A32+A33+A35+2*A31+A34$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A29	T-A32-A33-A35-A31-A34-A28-A30	L-A37	A65
R-L-A66	A38	T-S-A31	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15$	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	A31	L-T-A38	A66
R-L-A67	A39	T-S-A32	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	A32	L-T-A39	A67
R-L-A68	A40	T-S-A33	$A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16$	$S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	A33	L-T-A40	A68
R-L-A69	A41	T-S-A34	A1	$S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20$	$A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3$	A14	A18	A21	A34	L-T-A41	A69
R-L-A70	A42	T-S-A35	A2	A6	$S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8$	$A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S$	$S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14$	A22	A35	L-T-A42	A70
R-L-A71	A43	T-S-A30	A3	$A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S$	A10	$2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	A23	A30	L-T-A43	A71
$A72-A54-A55-2*A53+10*L-8*R-A63+A69+A70+A71+A67+A68+A64+A65+A66-A62-A61-A60-A59-A58-A57-A56$	A44	$A28+A30+7*S+A32+A33+A35+A31+A34-6*T$	$A25+A31-T-A30-4*S$	A25	$8*T-A29-2*A28-3*S-A27-A26-2*A25-A32-A33-A35-2*A31-A34$	A26	A27	A29	A28	L-T-A44	$A54-A72+A55+2*A53-11*L+9*R+A63-A69-A70-A71-A67-A68-A64-A65-A66+A62+A61+A60+A59+A58+A57+A56$
R-L-A72	$10*L-9*T-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44$	$27*T+A51+A50+A49+A47+A46+A45+A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A37-26*L+A48$	L-T-A45	L-T-A46	L-T-A47	L-T-A48	L-T-A49	L-T-A50	L-T-A51	$10*L-11*T$	A72
A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A60	A61	A62	A63	R-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62-A63

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of orders 8, 10 and 12 embedded with a magic square of order 6. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1), (2) and (3). The letters S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.22. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1), (2) and (3).

Example 3.22. Let's consider following two **semi-magic** and magic square based on the Result 3.22:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												120	mgc	L=5*R/6, T=4*L/5 and S=3*T/4												240
537	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-22	240	537	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-22	240		
-33	-100	-155	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	56	73	240	-33	-200	125	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-124	73	240		
-34	-124	33	605	36	-489	35	34	32	-116	154	74	240	-34	-114	3	645	6	-379	5	4	2	-126	154	74	240		
-35	47	30	77	13	16	20	24	-50	40	-17	75	240	-35	47	0	77	13	16	20	24	-30	40	-7	75	240		
-36	48	29	-5	14	17	21	25	28	41	-18	76	240	-36	48	-1	15	14	17	21	25	28	41	-8	76	240		
-37	49	28	-5	10	18	22	26	29	42	-19	77	240	-37	49	-2	-5	30	18	22	26	29	42	-9	77	240		
-38	50	27	10	-66	76	23	27	30	43	-20	78	240	-38	50	-3	10	-46	76	23	27	30	43	-10	78	240		
-39	51	26	11	15	-46	153	-64	31	44	-21	79	240	-39	51	-4	11	15	-26	133	-44	31	44	-11	79	240		
-40	52	31	12	114	19	-139	62	32	39	-22	80	240	-40	52	1	12	94	19	-99	62	32	39	-12	80	240		
-26	53	-34	-535	34	559	35	36	38	37	-23	66	240	-26	53	166	-605	34	419	35	36	38	37	-13	66	240		
-41	74	185	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	130	81	240	-41	164	-85	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	240	81	240		
62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-497	240	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-497	240		
16a	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	16b	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240		

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 170$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 200$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 240$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the conditions given in (1), (2) and (3).

Result 3.23. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49-L	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	11*L-9*R-A39
R-L-A50	10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A37-A36-A35-A33-A32-A31-A29-A30-A27-A28-A24-A25-A26-A23-A34	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23+18*T-17*L	A50
R-L-A51	A23-T	T-2*M-A21	12*M-6*T+A10+A11+A12+A13+A14+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19+A20+2*A21	T-2*M-A16	T-2*M-A17	T-2*M-A18	T-2*M-A19	T-2*M-A20	T-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14-A15-A21	L-A23	A51
R-L-A52	A24	T-2*M-A10	2*M/3-A6	A6+A7-M/3	2*M/3-A7	2*M/3-A2	A2+A3-M/3	2*M/3-A3	A10	L-T-A24	A52
R-L-A53	A25	T-2*M-A11	A6+A8-M/3	M+A1-A6-A7-A8	M/3+A7-A1	A2+A4-M/3	5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5	A3+A5-M/3	A11	L-T-A25	A53
R-L-A54	A26	T-2*M-A12	2*M/3-A8	M/3+A8-A1	A1	2*M/3-A4	A4+A5-M/3	2*M/3-A5	A12	L-T-A26	A54
R-L-A55	A27	T-2*M-A13	A2	M-A2-A3	A3	A6	M-A6-A7	A7	A13	L-T-A27	A55
R-L-A56	A28	T-2*M-A14	M-A2-A4	A2+A3+A4+A5-M	M-A3-A5	M-A6-A8	A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3	M/3-A7+A1	A14	L-T-A28	A56
R-L-A57	A29	T-2*M-A15	A4	M-A4-A5	A5	A8	M/3-A8+A1	2*M/3-A1	A15	L-T-A29	A57
10*L-8*R+A58+A56+A57+A54+A55+A51+A52+A53-A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40+A50-2*A39	A30	14*M-6*T+A10+A11+A12+A13+A14+A15+A21	7*(T-2*M)-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-2*A21	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	L-T-A30	9*R-A58-A57-A56-A55-A54-A53-A52-A51-A50+A49+A43+A40+A47+A48+A42+A44+A45+A46+A41-11*L+2*A39
R-L-A58	10*L-9*T-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30	27*T+A37+A36+A35+A33+A32+A31+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23-26*L+A34	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	10*L-11*T	A58
A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	R-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of orders 8, 10 and 12 embedded with a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again composed of four equal sums **semi-magic squares** of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the conditions given in (1), (2) and (3). The letters M, S, T, L and R represents respectively the **magic or semi-magic sums** of orders 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.23. First example is of **semi-magic squares** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1), (2) and (3).

Example 3.23. Let's consider following two **semi-magic and magic square** based on the Result 3.23:

semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												300	mgc	L=5*R/6, T=4*L/5 and S=3*T/4												300
1349	-87	-90	-93	-96	-99	-102	-105	-108	-111	-114	-124	220	1279	-77	-80	-83	-86	-89	-92	-95	-98	-101	-104	-74	300		
-117	-120	-795	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	332	157	220	-107	-250	-305	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	42	157	300		
-120	-74	-40	532	-25	-28	-31	-34	-37	-187	104	160	220	-110	-124	-20	412	-5	-8	-11	-14	-17	-137	174	160	300		
-123	79	-7	15	33	12	27	9	24	37	-49	163	220	-113	79	13	25	28	22	37	4	34	37	-29	163	300		
-126	82	-10	36	-14	38	12	30	18	40	-52	166	220	-116	82	10	31	1	43	7	55	13	40	-32	166	300		
-129	85	-13	9	41	10	21	21	18	43	-55	169	220	-119	85	7	19	46	10	31	16	28	43	-35	169	300		
-132	88	-16	13	31	16	25	7	28	46	-58	172	220	-122	88	4	13	46	16	25	22	28	46	-38	172	300		
-135	91	-19	28	10	22	4	54	2	49	-61	175	220	-125	91	1	43	-5	37	19	49	7	49	-41	175	300		
-138	94	-22	19	19	22	31	-1	30	52	-64	178	220	-128	94	-2	19	34	22	31	4	40	52	-44	178	300		
-92	97	277	-502	55	58	61	64	67	70	-67	132	220	-32	97	187	-362	55	58	61	64	67	70	-47	82	300		
-141	-242	825	-70	-73	-76	-79	-82	-85	-88	150	181	220	-131	8	355	-50	-53	-56	-59	-62	-65	-68	300	181	300		
124	127	130	133	136	139	142	145	148	151	154	-1309	220	124	127	130	133	136	139	142	145	148	151	154	-1229	300		
18a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	18b	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 60$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 150$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 180$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 220$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $S_{3 \times 3} = 75$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 200$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 250$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 300$. It is a magic square because it satisfied the conditions given in (1), (2) and (3).

Result 3.24. Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52-L$	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	$11*L-9*R-A42$
R-L-A53	$10*T-9*L$	$27*L-28*T-A40-A39-A38-A36-A35-A34-A32-A33-A30-A31-A27-A28-A29-A26-A37$	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26+18*T-17*L$	A53
R-L-A54	A26-T	T-S-A23	$2*T+3*S+A14-A20-A15$	T-S-A20	$A24+2*A23-7*T+2*S+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18$	T-S-A21	T-S-A22	T-S-A24	T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A14	L-A26	A54
R-L-A55	A27	T-S-A15	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A15	L-T-A27	A55
R-L-A56	A28	T-S-A16	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	A16	L-T-A28	A56
R-L-A57	A29	T-S-A17	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	A17	L-T-A29	A57
R-L-A58	A30	T-S-A18	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A18	L-T-A30	A58
R-L-A59	A31	T-S-A19	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	A19	L-T-A31	A59
R-L-A60	A32	T-S-A14	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	(S-M)/2	A14	L-T-A32	A60
$10*L-8*R+A61+A60+A59+A58+A57+A56+A55+A54+A53-A52-A51-A50-A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-2*A42$	A33	$A23+A14+7*S+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T$	$A20+A15-T-A14-4*S$	A20	$8*T-A24-2*A23-3*S-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18$	A21	A22	A24	A23	L-T-A33	$9*R-11*L-A61-A60-A59-A58-A57-A56-A55-A54-A53+A52+A51+A50+A49+A48+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+2*A42$
R-L-A61	$10*L-9*T-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$	$27*T+A40+A39+A38+A36+A35+A34+A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26-26*L+A37$	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$10*L-11*T$	A61
A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	R-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered semi-magic square embedded with single-digit bordered semi-magic squares of orders 8 and 10. These are semi-magic only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need all the three conditions given in (1), (2) and (3). See below two examples.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.24. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1), (2) and (3).

Example 3.24. *Let's consider a following semi-magic square based on the Result 3.24:*

2a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											160	2b	mgc	L=5*R/6, T=4*L/5 and S=3*T/4											240
	467	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-92	200		427	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-12	240
	-23	-140	35	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-64	63	200		-23	-200	275	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-204	63	240
	-24	-94	-3	529	0	-327	-1	-2	-4	-62	124	64	200		-24	-124	7	649	10	-497	9	8	6	-32	164	64	240
	-25	37	5	11	67	-11	13	0	20	25	-7	65	200		-25	37	15	11	87	-11	13	0	20	25	3	65	240
	-26	38	4	16	14	15	35	43	-23	26	-8	66	200		-26	38	14	16	14	15	55	43	-23	26	2	66	240
	-27	39	3	9	8	43	20	-1	21	27	-9	67	200		-27	39	13	9	8	63	20	-1	21	27	1	67	240
	-28	40	2	44	-9	33	12	-2	22	28	-10	68	200		-28	40	12	64	-9	33	12	-2	22	28	0	68	240
	-29	41	1	2	-34	71	1	10	50	29	-11	69	200		-29	41	11	2	-14	51	1	10	70	29	-1	69	240
	-30	42	6	18	54	-51	19	50	10	24	-12	70	200		-30	42	16	18	34	-31	19	70	10	24	-2	70	240
	-76	43	112	-499	30	357	31	32	34	33	-13	116	200		4	43	72	-609	30	537	31	32	34	33	-3	36	240
	-31	114	-5	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	170	71	200		-31	244	-235	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	240	71	240
	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	-427	200		52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	-387	240
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

- (i) The *magic and semi-magic sums* of the first example are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 100$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 130$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 160$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 200$. In this case there is only one *cornered* magic square of order 6 with magic rectangles sums $MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$
- (ii) The *magic sums* of the first example are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1), (2) and (3). Moreover, in this case there is only one *cornered* magic square of order 6 with magic rectangles sums $MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$. It is a magic square as it satisfies all the four the conditions given in (1).

3.4 Four-Conditions Magic Squares

Below are results with examples of **semi-magic** squares resulting in magic squares with two conditions given in (1), (2), (3) and (4).

Result 3.25. Let's consider following *semi-magic* square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57-L$	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	$11*L-9*R-A47$
R-L-A58	$10*T+A46-9*L$	$27*L-2*A46-28*T-A45-A44-A43-A41-A40-A39-A37-A38-A35-A36-A32-A33-A34-A31-A42$	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$A46+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+18*T-17*L$	A58
R-L-A59	A31-T	T-S-A27	$2*T+3*S+A17-2*A14-A24-2*A13-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A18-2*A15$	T-S-A24	$A28+2*A27+2*A14-7*T+2*S+A26+A25+2*A24+2*A13+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A19+A20+A22+2*A18+2*A15+A21$	T-S-A25	T-S-A26	T-S-A28	T-A19-A20-A22-A18-A21-A27-A17	L-A31	A59
R-L-A60	A32	T-S-A18	S-M-A15	S-A13-M	$2*A11-3*A4-A13-A8+A9+M$	$3*A4-3*S+2*A13+A14+2*A8+A9-A10+2*A15+2*M$	S-A14-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A15	A18	L-T-A32	A60
R-L-A61	A33	T-S-A19	S-M-A9	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A9	A19	L-T-A33	A61
R-L-A62	A34	T-S-A20	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A20	L-T-A34	A62
R-L-A63	A35	T-S-A21	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A11	A21	L-T-A35	A63
R-L-A64	A36	T-S-A22	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A8	A22	L-T-A36	A64
R-L-A65	A37	T-S-A17	$A8-4*S+A9+A10+A11+A15+5*M$	A13	$S-2*A11+3*A4+A13+A8-A9-2*M$	$4*S+A11-3*A4-2*A13-A14-2*A8-A10-2*A15-3*M$	A14	A15	A17	L-T-A37	A65
$10*L-8*R+A66+A65+A64+A63+A62+A61+A60+A59+A58-A57-A56-A55-A54-A53-A52-A51-A50-A49-A48-2*A47$	A38	$A27+A17+7*S+A19+A20+A22+A18+A21-6*T$	$A24+2*A13+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A18+2*A15-T-A17+2*A14-4*S$	A24	$8*T-A28-2*A27-2*A14-3*S-A26-A25-2*A24-2*A13-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A19-A20-A22-2*A18-2*A15-A21$	A25	A26	A28	A27	L-T-A38	$9*R-11*L-A66-A65-A64-A63-A62-A61-A60-A59-A58+A57+A56+A55+A54+A53+A52+A51+A50+A49+A48+2*A47$
R-L-A66	$10*L-9*T-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A46$	$27*T+2*A46+A45+A44+A43+A41+A40+A39+A37+A38+A35+A36+A32+A33+A34+A31-26*L+A42$	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	L-T-A42	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	$10*L-11*T-A46$	A66
A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	R-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered semi-magic square embedded with single-digit bordered semi-magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10. These are semi-magic only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need all the four conditions given in (1), (2), (3) and (4). See below two examples.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3.25. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1), (2), (3) and (4).

Example 3.25. *Let's consider a following semi-magic square based on the Result 3.25:*

1a	semi	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											100	1b	mgc	L=5*R/6, T=4*L/5, S=3*T/4 and M=2*S/3											240
	532	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-207	200		482	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-17	240
	-18	-94	-142	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	22	68	200		-28	-144	88	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-108	68	240
	-19	-79	-17	-67	-14	361	-15	-16	-18	-94	109	69	200		-29	-119	3	23	6	171	5	4	2	-54	159	69	240
	-20	42	-8	5	7	48	37	6	-3	28	-12	70	200		-30	42	12	15	17	58	-3	16	17	28	-2	70	240
	-21	43	-9	11	11	57	-11	13	19	29	-13	71	200		-31	43	11	21	11	67	-11	13	19	29	-3	71	240
	-22	44	-10	10	16	14	15	25	20	30	-14	72	200		-32	44	10	20	16	14	15	35	20	30	-4	72	240
	-23	45	-11	9	9	8	33	20	21	31	-15	73	200		-33	45	9	19	9	8	43	20	21	31	-5	73	240
	-24	46	-12	12	34	-9	33	12	18	32	-16	74	200		-34	46	8	22	44	-9	33	12	18	32	-6	74	240
	-25	47	-7	53	23	-18	-7	24	25	27	-17	75	200		-35	47	13	23	23	-18	43	24	25	27	-7	75	240
	-191	48	194	87	34	-341	35	36	38	37	-18	241	200		-11	48	94	17	34	-131	35	36	38	37	-8	51	240
	-26	8	172	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	124	76	200		-36	148	-48	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	184	76	240
	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	-482	200		57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	-442	240
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

- (i) The magic and semi-magic sums of the first example are $M_{4 \times 4} = 70$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} = 100$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} = 120$, $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} = 150$ and $R_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} = 200$.
- (ii) The magic sums of the second example are $M_{4 \times 4} = 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} = 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} = 160$, $L_{10 \times 10} = 200$ and $R_{12 \times 12} = 240$. It is a magic square as it satisfies all the four the conditions given in (1), (2), (3) and (4).

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** lease see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <http://bit.ly/415ozRt>
 - (ii) <http://bit.ly/4kU3QHf>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <http://bit.ly/3H06Unn>
 - (ii) <http://bit.ly/46WEntx>

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